

TERN Monitoring in the Pilbara region, Western Australia

**Summary of surveys completed to inform the West Australian
Vegetation Extent (WAVE) Pilot Project 2025**

Final Report April 2026

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The fieldwork presented in this report was conducted under applicable Western Australian Government permits to undertake scientific research (Regulation 4 Lawful Authority, PILCALMR4-2025/0015 and PILCALMR4-2025/0008) and collect flora samples (Regulation 61 Flora Taking [Other Purposes] Licence FT61001649, FT61001651 and FT61001650).

Photographs presented in this report were contributed by TERN personnel. Photographs may be available for use, please contact TERN tern@adelaide.edu.au. For more information regarding this document, please contact tern@adelaide.edu.au

Front cover photograph: *Triodia hummock* grassland, Bonney Downs Station, Western Australia (credit: Kirrily Blaylock, TERN).

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1 Introduction

In 2025 the Western Australian Department of Water and Environmental Regulation (DWER) provided funding to TERN to conduct ecological surveys and uncrewed aerial vehicle (UAV) surveys in the Pilbara bioregion. These surveys were conducted in part to collect information that can be used as training and validation data for the Western Australian Vegetation Extent (WAVE) pilot project. This document provides a summary of the surveys completed and data collected between April and July 2025.

Data from the surveys conducted will be available via the [TERN Data Discovery Portal](https://portal.tern.org.au/)<https://portal.tern.org.au/>. The samples collected are housed at the [TERN Australia Soil and Herbarium Collection](#) at The Adelaide University and are openly available to researchers by application.

2 Background and Context

2.1 TERN ecosystem monitoring

TERN is an Australian Government National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)-funded environmental monitoring project. TERN collects long-term ecosystem data and samples from around Australia using highly instrumented monitoring sites, field surveys and remote-sensing techniques such as drones and satellites. TERN shares these data to enable Australia's world-leading research on climate, biodiversity, and soil. For more information on TERN, visit tern.org.au.

TERN conducts long-term monitoring of a network of plots across Australia using standardised field survey protocols. These protocols were co-created with the assistance of state and territory experts, representatives of the federal environment department and academic experts from across the country. The protocols were originally published in 2012 in the *AusPlots Rangelands Survey Protocols Manual* (White et al.), which is available for download from the [TERN website](#). Further information on the rationale for the method is available in *Sparrow et al.* (2020).

From 2025, the TERN monitoring methods were updated to modernise the in-field data collection systems, with the field team using a new web-app. Methods align with the original AusPlots methods and also with the newly published Ecological Monitoring System Australia (EMSA). EMSA is an ecological field survey protocol and data system that was developed by TERN in collaboration with the Australian Government Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW) to support the Australian Government Natural Resource Management investment programs. Many of the modules included in EMSA's *Ecological Field Monitoring Protocols Manual* (O'Neill et. al 2024), which is available for download from the [EMSA website](#), are components of the AusPlots Rangelands methods.

DroneScape, (TERN's UAV capability) became operational in 2024. Standardised [protocols](#) for UAV data collection have been established by industry experts, enabling the DroneScape team to collect accurate, repeatable and reliable data from across Australia. "DroneScape is aimed at incorporating drone-generated, analysis-ready products into the [TERN] standard ecosystem monitoring toolkit" (University of Tasmania 2025).

2.2 WAVE Project

The Western Australian Government uses vegetation extent mapping and monitoring information to inform regulation, approvals and policy decisions. However, there is no current state-wide vegetation extent or change mapping that is publicly available, regularly updated and at a scale relevant to land management. To address this, the Government is piloting a Western Australia Vegetation Extent (WAVE) dataset and system; developing semi-automated methods leveraging remote sensing and machine learning to provide reliable, accessible and regularly updated information on Western Australian native vegetation status and trends. The purpose of the WAVE Pilot is to inform the design and business case for the funding and establishment of a new, ongoing mapping service for the State.

The Pilbara bioregion is one of three pilot regions for the WAVE Pilot project. TERN Australia was contracted to conduct on-ground ecological field surveys, and UAV surveys in the Pilbara, to provide data for the pilot. The results of the surveys are presented in this report.

More information about the WAVE Pilot can be found on the [project webpage](#).

2.3 Permits and land access permissions

TERN surveys are conducted in accordance with the relevant federal and state permitting frameworks. The 2025 Pilbara surveys were conducted under the following permits:

- Regulation 4 Lawful Authority (PILCALMR4-2025/0015 and PILCALMR4-2025/0008)
- Regulation 61 Flora Taking (Other Purposes) Licence (FT61001649, FT61001651 and FT61001650).

Land access permissions were obtained from all landowners and Native title representative bodies prior to the surveys. Other parties notified of planned surveys included mining tenement holders.

3 Survey Methods

3.1 Summary of vegetation survey methods

At each survey site, a one-hectare plot (100 m x 100 m) was established using the EMSA Plot Selection and Layout Module (see McCallum et al. 2024a for detailed information). At each plot, standardised landscape information was recorded following the EMSA Plot Description Module (Enhanced protocol), including landform and land surface characteristics, vegetation community description and site disturbance observations. Minor modifications to the published version of the methods (see McCallum et al. 2024b) were made to suit the WAVE project data needs. Instead of a basic structural summary being recorded, a full community description equivalent to NVIS Level 5 was recorded. Climatic conditions prior to the field survey were also recorded.

At each plot, vegetation and substrate cover was collected using the EMSA Cover Module (Standard protocol) (see Laws et al. 2023 for detailed information). Information collected consisted of substrate type and growth form, height and fractional cover type (photosynthetic vegetation or non-photosynthetic vegetation) of intercepted vascular plants along four 100-metre transects.

All vascular flora species present within plots were collected using the EMSA Floristics Module (Enhanced protocol) (see Laws et al. 2024). Vouchers of all plant species located within the plot were taken for identification by botanists at the Western Australian Herbarium. Information

collected for each voucher includes habit, life stage, and phenological traits. In situ photographs of some species were also collected to facilitate identification.

A [photo-panorama](#) (a series of overlapping photographs that can be stitched together to form a single 360° photo-panorama) was taken at the centre point of each plot.

3.2 UAV survey methods

During the 2025 surveys, the TERN collected high-resolution RGB imagery, 10-band multispectral imagery, and LiDAR data using the following equipment and methods:

- Equipment:
 - Two DJI Enterprise [Matrice 350 RTK](#) (M350) drone platforms
 - DJI Enterprise [Zenmuse P1](#): Collects high-resolution RGB imagery
 - DJI Enterprise [Zenmuse L2](#): Collects LiDAR point cloud data
 - AgEagle Aerial Systems, Inc. MicaSense series [RedEdge-P](#) Dual: Collects 10 bands of multispectral
 - DJI Enterprise [D-RTK 2](#) GNSS receiver used to ensure centimetre-level positioning data
- [LiDAR data collection](#)
 - Equipment: DJI M350 UAV
 - DJI Enterprise L2 sensor
 - Flight elevation: 50 m above ground level (AGL)
 - Flight area: 100 m margin of 1-hectare plot (300 m x 300 m total)
 - Flight time: approximately 20 minutes
- [RGB and multispectral collection](#)
 - Equipment: DJI M350 UAV fitted with DJI P1 and RedEdge-P Dual
 - Flight elevation: 80 m AGL
 - Flight area: 100 m margin of 1-ha plot (300 m x 300 m total)
 - Flight time: approximately 15 minutes.

4 Plot Locations

4.1 Existing TERN plots

Prior to 2025, TERN had previously established 35 monitoring plots in the Pilbara (19 in 2015, 16 in 2016). These sites were co-located with sites that had previously been surveyed by the WA Department of Environment and Conservation and the Western Australian Museum for the Pilbara Biodiversity Survey (McKenzie et al. 2009).

Figure 1. TERN plot network in the Pilbara

shows the locations of these plots. Appendix 1 provides survey dates, location information, and the broad floristic formation of these plots. Data and samples collected during previous surveys of these plots can be accessed via the [TERN EcoPlots](#).

Figure 1. TERN plot network in the Pilbara

4.2 New plots established to meet WAVE objectives

Under the partnership with DWER for the WAVE project, TERN established 41 new survey plots in seven properties and management areas across the Pilbara in 2025.

Figure 1. TERN plot network in the Pilbara

shows the locations of these plots within the Pilbara bioregion.

Location selection for new plots consisted of two levels of stratification, based initially on property and management area selection, and refined by plot placement.

4.2.1 Property/management area selection

The areas where new plots were established were selected by DWER with the intention of situating plots in areas where the collected data could be used for multiple purposes, and by many different collaborators. Considerations for selection included:

- Land tenure type and access permissions
- Traditional Owner engagement and support
- Other WA State Government and local project partner priorities.

4.2.2 Plot placement

Once the properties were identified and access negotiated, potential plot locations were identified from aerial imagery, targeting areas of grasslands and open shrublands (known data gaps for the WAVE pilot). The TERN team then further refined the site selection by visiting the proposed sites and conducting a ground-truthing assessment to ensure the sites selected matched the expected vegetation units. Traditional Owners and Indigenous Rangers assisted with plot placement by generously sharing their knowledge of vegetation communities and by guiding the team to avoid culturally sensitive areas. Considerations for plot placement included:

- Road access – plots were ideally placed at least 100 m away from tracks.
- Disturbance – plots were placed in areas with low existing disturbance and away from sources of potential disturbance.
- Vegetation community type and homogeneity – grasslands and open low shrublands were targeted to fill known data gaps for the WAVE pilot. Plots were placed in homogeneous areas, ideally within larger areas of the same vegetation type.
- Cultural heritage areas – when Traditional Owners were unable to accompany the team during surveys, sites were placed in consideration of registered and lodged cultural heritage areas included in the Department of Land Planning and Heritage Aboriginal Cultural Heritage Inquiry System (ACHIS).

New plots were established in the following areas:

- Ex-Hamersley Station – Eastern Guruma Country (Figure 2)
 - Partners in selecting the area, coordinating access and placing plots included DWER, DBCA, the Pilbara Environmental Offset Fund (PEOF) and Eastern Guruma Traditional Owners.
- Karijini National Park (Figure 3)
 - Partners in selecting the area and coordinating access included DWER and DBCA.
- Cane River Conservation Park – Thalanyji Country (Figure 4)
 - Partners in selecting the area, coordinating access and placing plots included DWER, DBCA and Thalanyji Traditional Owners.
- Tharra/Woodstock-Abydos Protected Area – Palyku Country (Figure 5)
 - Partners in selecting the area, coordinating access and placing plots included DWER, PEOF, Palyku Traditional Owners and Budadee Rangers.

- Purungunya Conservation Estate – Nyamal Country (Figure 6)
 - Partners in selecting the area, coordinating access, and placing plots included DWER, DBCA, PEOF, Nyamal Traditional Owners and Nyamal Rangers.
- Bonney Downs Station (Figure 7)
 - Partners in selecting the area and coordinating access included DWER, Pilbara Innovation Partnership's Pilbara Extension Network and station management.
- Eginbah (Limestone) Station (Figure 8)
 - Partners in selecting the area and coordinating access included DWER, Pilbara Innovation Partnership's Pilbara Extension Network and station management.

Figure 2. Map of TERN plots on Ex-Hamersley Station – Eastern Guruma Country

Figure 3. Map of TERN plots in Karijini National Park

Figure 4. Map of TERN plots in Cane River Conservation Park – Thalanyji Country

Figure 5. Map of TERN plots in Tharra/Woodstock-Abydos Protected Area – Palyku Country

Figure 6. Map of TERN plots on Purungunya Conservation Estate – Nyamal Country

Figure 7. Map of TERN plots on Bonney Downs Station

Figure 8. Map of TERN plots on Eginbah (Limestone) Station

5 Surveys Conducted in 2025

In 2025, TERN Ecosystem Surveillance teams completed vegetation surveys at 41 plots and UAV surveys at 71 plots in the Pilbara. Table 1 lists the 74 plots surveyed in 2025. Appendix 1 provides survey dates, location information, and broad floristic formation of all 76 TERN plots within the Pilbara. Appendix 2 provides detailed plot description information for the plots surveyed in 2025.

Table 1. TERN Plots in the Pilbara bioregion surveyed in 2025 for the WAVE project

Plot	Property	2025 Vegetation Survey	2025 UAV Survey
WAAPIL0001	Karijini National Park	-	29/05/2025
WAAPIL0002	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	1/07/2025
WAAPIL0003	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	1/07/2025
WAAPIL0004	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	2/07/2025
WAAPIL0005	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	1/07/2025
WAAPIL0006	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	1/07/2025
WAAPIL0007	Water Supply Reserve	-	1/07/2025
WAAPIL0008	Coolawanyah Station	-	30/06/2025
WAAPIL0009	Coolawanyah Station	-	30/06/2025
WAAPIL0010	Mount Florence Station	-	3/06/2025
WAAPIL0011	Mount Florence Station	-	3/06/2025
WAAPIL0012	Karijini National Park	-	29/05/2025
WAAPIL0014	Karijini National Park	-	29/05/2025
WAAPIL0015	Hamersley Station	-	1/06/2025
WAAPIL0016	Karijini National Park	-	30/05/2025
WAAPIL0017	Mulga Downs Station	-	29/06/2025
WAAPIL0018	Mulga Downs Station	-	28/05/2025
WAAPIL0019	Mulga Downs Station	-	28/05/2025
WAAPIL0020	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	2/07/2025
WAAPIL0021	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	2/07/2025
WAAPIL0022	Millstream Chichester National Park	-	2/07/2025
WAAPIL0023	Mulga Downs Station	-	29/06/2025
WAAPIL0024	Marillana Station / Fortescue Marsh	-	29/06/2025
WAAPIL0025	Roy Hill Station	-	26/07/2025
WAAPIL0026	Marillana Station	-	26/07/2025
WAAPIL0027	Roy Hill Station	-	26/07/2025
WAAPIL0028	Roy Hill Station	-	26/07/2025
WAAPIL0029	Roy Hill Station	-	26/07/2025
WAAPIL0030	RioTinto Mining Lease	-	27/07/2025
WAAPIL0031	RioTinto Mining Lease	-	28/07/2025
WAAPIL0032	RioTinto Mining Lease	-	28/07/2025
WAAPIL0033	RioTinto Mining Lease	-	28/07/2025
WAAPIL0034	RioTinto Mining Lease	-	27/07/2025
WAAPIL0036	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex-Hamersley Station	30/04/2025	2/06/2025
WAAPIL0037	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex-Hamersley Station	30/04/2025	1/06/2025
WAAPIL0038	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex-Hamersley Station	1/05/2025	1/06/2025
WAAPIL0039	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex-Hamersley Station	1/05/2025	2/06/2025
WAAPIL0040	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	31/05/2025
WAAPIL0041	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	31/05/2025

Plot	Property	2025 Vegetation Survey	2025 UAV Survey
WAAPIL0042	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	31/05/2025
WAAPIL0043	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	4/06/2025
WAAPIL0044	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	4/06/2025
WAAPIL0045	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	4/06/2025
WAAPIL0046	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	28/05/2025	23/07/2025
WAAPIL0047	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	29/05/2025	23/07/2025
WAAPIL0048	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	29/05/2025	24/07/2025
WAAPIL0049	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	23/07/2025
WAAPIL0050	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	23/07/2025
WAAPIL0051	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	23/07/2025
WAAPIL0052	Purungunya Conservation Estate	1/06/2025	25/06/2025
WAAPIL0053	Purungunya Conservation Estate	1/06/2025	25/06/2025
WAAPIL0054	Purungunya Conservation Estate	2/06/2025	26/06/2025
WAAPIL0055	Purungunya Conservation Estate	2/06/2025	26/06/2025
WAAPIL0056	Purungunya Conservation Estate	3/06/2025	26/06/2025
WAAPIL0057	Purungunya Conservation Estate	3/06/2025	25/06/2025
WAAPIL0058	Purungunya Conservation Estate	4/06/2025	25/06/2025
WAAPIL0059	Eginbah Station	25/06/2025	26/06/2025
WAAPIL0060	Eginbah Station	25/06/2025	27/06/2025
WAAPIL0061	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	27/06/2025
WAAPIL0062	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	27/06/2025
WAAPIL0063	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	27/06/2025
WAAPIL0064	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	28/06/2025
WAAPIL0065	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	28/06/2025
WAAPIL0066	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	28/06/2025
WAAPIL0067	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-
WAAPIL0068	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-
WAAPIL0069	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-
WAAPIL0070	Bonney Downs Station	30/06/2025	-
WAAPIL0071	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	25/07/2025
WAAPIL0072	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	25/07/2025
WAAPIL0073	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	25/07/2025
WAAPIL0074	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	25/07/2025
WAAPIL0075	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	25/07/2025
WAAPIL0076	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	25/07/2025
- Not surveyed in 2025			

5.1 Survey summary

From April through July 2025, TERN completed six surveys in the Pilbara, accomplishing the following:

- Collected point-intercept data along 16.4 km of transects
- Conducted drone flights over approximately 875 km
- Collected 1,099 plant specimens representing 296 taxa
- Drove 8,600 kilometres back and forth across the Pilbara (Figures 9-14 vegetation surveys 1-3 and Figures 15-17 UAV surveys 1-3).

A summary of the survey work completed for each survey conducted is presented below (Tables 2-4 vegetation surveys 1-3 and Tables 5-7 UAV surveys 1-3).

5.2 Vegetation survey 1

Table 2. Summary of Vegetation Survey 1

Dates	28 April to 9 May
Properties/Management areas visited	Ex-Hamersley Station, Karijini National Park, Cane River Conservation Park
Number of plots established	10
Plant specimens collected	304
Distance driven	1,220 km
Nights camping	6
Collaborators in attendance	Eastern Gumura Traditional Owners advised on plot placement at Ex-Hamersley Station

Figure 9. Vegetation Survey 1 driving route

Figure 10. TERN staff working on Ex-Hamersley Station
(photo credit: Kirrily Blaylock/TERN)

5.3 Vegetation survey 2

Table 3. Summary of Vegetation Survey 2

Dates	26 May to 6 June
Properties/Management areas visited	Tharra/Woodstock-Abydos Protected Area, Purungunya Conservation Estate
Number of plots established	13
Plant specimens collected	351
Distance driven	1,260 km
Nights camping	8
Collaborators in attendance	Budadee Rangers advised on plot placement at Tharra Nyamal Rangers advised on plot placement at Purungunya

Figure 11. Vegetation Survey 2 driving route

Figure 12. TERN staff with Nyamal Ranger Adrian Taylor (pictured with permission) at Purungunya Conservation Estate

(photo credit: Donna Lewis/TERN)

5.4 Vegetation survey 3

Table 4. Summary of Vegetation Survey 3

Dates	23 June to 4 July
Properties/Management areas visited	Eginbah (Limestone) Station, Bonney Downs Station
Number of plots established	18
Distance driven	1,335 km
Plant specimens collected	444
Nights camping	10
Collaborators in attendance	Helen Vonow, SA Herbarium Collections Manager, attended the field trip as a volunteer 5 plots on Eginbah Station placed in consultation with station management in area of pilot grazing management plan Bonney Downs station management attended one site

Figure 13. Vegetation Survey 3 driving route

Figure 14. TERN staff working on Bonney Downs Station
(photo credit: Kirily Blaylock/TERN)

5.5 UAV survey 1

Table 5. Summary of UAV Survey 1

Dates	26 May to 6 June
Properties/Management areas visited	Mulga Downs Station, Karijini National Park, Ex-Hamersley Station, Mount Florence Station, Cane River Conservation Park
Number of plots surveyed	19
Distance flown by UAVs	237.5 km
Distance driven	1,770 km
Nights camping	5

One additional plot in Karijini National Park was planned for UAV survey but could not be safely accessed.

Figure 15. TERN staff landing a drone
(photo credit: Troy Bektas/TERN)

5.6 UAV survey 2

Table 6. Summary of UAV survey 2

Dates	23 June to 4 July
Properties/Management areas visited	Purungunya Conservation Estate, Millstream Chichester National Park, Eginbah (Limestone) Station, Coolawanyah Station, Mulga Downs Station
Number of plots surveyed	29
Distance flown by UAVs	362.5 km
Distance driven	2,265 km
Nights camping	6

Figure 16. TERN UAV survey on Eginbah Station

(photo credit: Carla Franson/TERN)

5.7 UAV survey 3

Table 7. Summary of UAV survey 3

Dates	21-31 July
Properties/Management areas visited	Tharra/Woodstock-Abydos Protected Area, Bonney Downs Station, Roy Hill Station, Unallocated Crown Land
Number of plots surveyed	22
Distance flown by UAVs	275 km
Kilometres driven	750 km
Nights camping	5

One additional plot on unallocated Crown land was planned for survey but authorisation to conduct UAV surveys was not granted by the lease holder.

Four additional plots on Bonney Downs Station were planned for survey but could not be surveyed due to mustering activity.

Figure 17. TERN UAV surveyor holding a staff used to collect site altitude data (photo credit: Carla Franson/TERN)

6 Plot Summaries

A summary of all TERN plots in the Pilbara is included in Appendix 1, including survey dates, location information, and National Vegetation Information System (NVIS) broad floristics formation (NVIS Technical Working Group, 2017). Broad floristic formation is level 3 of the NVIS vegetation hierarchy and includes dominant genus and structural formation for the structurally dominant stratum. For plots WAAPIL0001 to WAAPIL0035, the NVIS broad floristic formation and association is automated based on quantitative data collected across the plot during surveys conducted prior to 2025. For plots sampled during 2025, the broad floristic formation and association is a field observation based on the recognition of strata, dominant growth form and species per strata, estimated cover and height for each stratum documented.

Detailed summaries of all plots surveyed in 2025, and plots sampled in either 2015, 2016 or 2021 for plots visited in 2025 (excluding WAAPIL0013 and WAAPIL0035) are provided in Appendix 2. Appendix 2 includes NVIS broad floristic formation, survey dates, landform pattern and element, property, plot coordinates, vegetation community description and a representative photo of the plot. The vegetation community description is based on NVIS level 5 associations (per Lewis et al. 2024 and NVIS Technical Working Group 2017). An association includes up to three dominant species for up to three dominant strata, and each stratum is given a structural formation from estimated stratum heights and cover. The dominant stratum is indicated with a '+,' and species are listed in order of dominance. For plots where UAV surveys but not vegetation surveys were conducted in 2025, data collected during previous surveys is presented.

7 Species Summary

A summary of the number of species recorded, herbarium specimens collected, WA Priority Listed species, introduced species (alien to WA), and number of phrase name taxa recorded by year of sampling, for all TERN surveys completed to date are presented in Table 8. Over the four years of sampling (2015, 2016, 2021 and 2025), a total 617 vascular flora species were recorded, representing over a quarter of the vascular flora known in the Pilbara.

A total 296 species were recorded during the 2025 field surveys and 1,099 herbarium specimens collected, mostly all housed in the TERN Australia Soil and Herbarium Collection with exchange specimens provided to PERTH (WA Herbarium), CANB (Australian National Herbarium) and AD (State Herbarium of South Australia). Across the four years, almost 4,000 herbarium specimens were collected. The collections are available for downstream research.

Of note, a total 26 phrase name taxa were identified over the four sampling years, with 11 from the 2025 field surveys. Phrase name taxa are temporary names given to an undescribed species, used to manage unnamed taxa prior to formal publication. In WA phrase name taxa represent a significant portion of the WA flora (Florabase, 2026).

Plant species lists for all plots surveyed in 2025, 2021, 2016 and 2015 are included in Appendix 3 including taxon name, family, year sampled, introduced species flag (*) and Priority Listed taxa labelled (P1, P2, P3, P4). Taxonomy largely follows the Australian Plant Census (APC) and for the purpose of WAVE, follows Florabase, the authoritative, dynamic online resource for WA plant taxonomy (Census of Western Australian Plants; Florabase, 2026).

Table 8. Summary of number of species recorded, herbarium specimen collections, priority listed species, introduced status and phrase name taxa by year of sampling.

Survey Year	No. of plots	No. of species	No. of collections	No. of WA Priority Listed species	No. of Introduced species (Alien to WA)	No. of phrase name taxa
2025	41	296	1,099	5	5	11
2021	14 revisits	266	855	2	10	11
2016	16	295	810	3	7	10
2015	19	400	1,096	11	17	14
TOTAL (unique)	76	617	3,860	19	20	26

Across the four years of surveys, there were no threatened species detected under the WA *Biodiversity Conservation Act 2016* (BC Act) or Commonwealth legislation, *Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999* (EPBC Act). Although, in WA there are Priority Listings which is not a listing under the BC Act, even though all flora are protected in WA. The protection applies even when a species is not listed as threatened or specially protected, and regardless of land tenure (State managed land [Crown land], private land, or Commonwealth land).

Species that may possibly be threatened species that do not meet the criteria for listing under the BC Act because of insufficient survey or are otherwise data deficient, are added to the Priority Flora Lists under Priorities 1, 2, 3 or 4 (State of Western Australia, 2025). The categories are defined on the DBCA [website](#).

Table 9 provides the 18 Priority Listed taxa recorded across the four sampling years. In 2025, one Priority 1 (*Acacia aphanoclada*), and four Priority 3 (*Goodenia obscurata*, *Senna* sp. Barlee Range (S. van Leeuwen 1520), *Streptoglossa* sp. Cracking clays (S. van Leeuwen et al. PBS 7353) and *Themeda* sp. Hamersley Station (M.E. Trudgen11431) listed taxa were identified.

Table 9. WA Priority Listed species by year of sampling.

Priority listed species	WA Status	2025 occurrence	2021 occurrence	2016 occurrence	2015 occurrence
<i>Acacia aphanoclada</i>	P1	X			
<i>Aristida jerichoensis</i> var. <i>subspinulifera</i>	P3		X		X
<i>Cladium procerum</i>	P2				X
<i>Eremophila magnifica</i> subsp. <i>magnifica</i>	P4				X
<i>Eremophila youngii</i> subsp. <i>lepidota</i>	P4			X	X
<i>Euphorbia stevenii</i>	P3				X
<i>Goodenia obscurata</i>	P3	X			
<i>Isotropis forrestii</i>	P2				X
<i>Livistona alfredii</i>	P4			X	X
<i>Senna</i> sp. Barlee Range (S. van Leeuwen 1520)	P3	X			
<i>Sida</i> sp. Barlee Range (S. van Leeuwen 1642)	P4		X		
<i>Sida</i> sp. Hamersley Range (K. Newbey 10692)	P3				X
<i>Solanum albostellatum</i>	P3			X	
<i>Streptoglossa</i> sp. Cracking clays (S. van Leeuwen et al. PBS 7353)	P3	X			
<i>Swainsona thompsoniana</i>	P3				X
<i>Teucrium pilbaranum</i>	P2				X
<i>Themeda</i> sp. Hamersley Station (M.E. Trudgen11431)	P3	X			
<i>Tribulus adelacanthus</i>	P3			X	
<i>Vittadinia</i> sp. Coondewanna Flats (S. van Leeuwen)	P3				X
TOTAL		5	2	3	11

According to Keighery (2010), 103 introduced species are established in the Pilbara with the number of new incursions increasing at a rate of seven to 11 species per year. Across the four years of surveys, 20 introduced species were identified according Florabase (2026; Table 10). Five introduced species were recorded during the 2025 field surveys.

The most frequent introduced species occurrences across all sampling years include *Cenchrus ciliaris* (Buffel Grass), *Cenchrus setiger* (Birdwood Grass), *Malvastrum americanum* (Spiked Malvastrum) and *Vachellia farnesiana*.

Table 10. Introduced species by year of sampling.

Introduced species (Alien to WA)	Common Name	2025 occurrence	2021 occurrence	2016 occurrence	2015 occurrence
<i>Aerva javanica</i>	Kapok Bush	X	X	X	
<i>Bidens bipinnata</i>	Bipinnate Beggartick		X		
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	Cobbler's Pegs		X		
<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i>	Buffel Grass	X	X	X	X
<i>Cenchrus setiger</i>	Birdwood Grass	X	X	X	X
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	Sunnhemp		X		X
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Couch				X
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Awnless Barnyard				X
<i>Flaveria trinervia</i>	Speedy Weed		X		X
<i>Lactuca serriola</i>	Prickly Lettuce				X
<i>Malvastrum americanum</i>	Spiked Malvastrum	X	X	X	X
<i>Passiflora foetida</i> var. <i>hispida</i>					X
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Date Palm				X
<i>Portulaca pilosa</i>	Djanggar				X
<i>Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum</i>	Jersey Cudweed				X
<i>Rumex vesicarius</i>	Ruby Dock				X
<i>Setaria verticillata</i>	Whorled Pigeon		X	X	X
<i>Sigesbeckia orientalis</i>	Indian Weed				X
<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	Common Sowthistle			X	X
<i>Vachellia farnesiana</i>		X	X	X	X
TOTAL (by year)		5	10	7	17

8 Example Data Uses Beyond WAVE

Whilst the primary purpose of the surveys conducted and presented in this report is to inform the WAVE pilot project, the data has many other potential future uses. This section describes some of the uses of TERN's research infrastructure, which these data, samples, and specimens now form part of, to illustrate those potential uses.

TERN's Ecosystem Monitoring plot survey data are used in a wide range of ecological and biodiversity research, including vegetation structure, species richness, soil characteristics, taxonomy, and ecosystem dynamics. Researchers use it to understand plant-soil interactions, carbon and nutrient budgets, vegetation distribution and threats to biodiversity. For example, recent notable work on the photosynthetic pathways of Australian plant species used TERN plot data and stable isotope analysis to classify over 4,800 plant species into C3, C4, and CAM photosynthetic types (Munroe et al. 2022). This research contributed to the development of isoscapes (spatial maps of isotopic variation) across Australia, thereby enhancing our understanding of plant functional traits, ecological adaptation, and biogeographic patterns in response to climate and environmental gradients.¹

TERN data contribute to long-term climate and ecological change monitoring, providing critical data that enable researchers to investigate ecosystem responses to climate variation across bioregions. It helps identify ecological thresholds, resilience patterns, and adaptation potential of species and communities. TERN's collection of plant specimens enables scientists to model and

¹ For more information on this research, see: <https://www.tern.org.au/news/a-vegetation-carbon-isoscape-for-australia/>.

predict plant responses and resilience to climate change, as demonstrated by recent research that analysed variation in plant traits from over 700 species to reveal predictable relationships between traits and environmental changes (Dong et al. 2020).²

TERN provides policy and management support, and TERN data is used by government agencies for environmental reporting, impact assessments, and conservation planning. It informs decisions on land management, restoration, and sustainable development. TERN contributes to the Australian Government's State of the Environment (SoE) reporting by providing monitoring data for key environmental indicators that reflect the condition and trends of Australia's ecosystems. These indicators are used in both national SoE reports and the annual *Australia's Environment* reports produced by TERN in collaboration with the Australian National University.³

8.1 Data availability and sample access

Data collected from the WAVE pilot project surveys conducted by TERN are available from the [TERN Data Discovery Portal](#). TERN data is also accessible from the TERN Australia [ausplots R](#) package.

The TERN plant voucher specimens collected for the WAVE pilot project are held in the [TERN Australia Soil and Herbarium Collection](#). Plant voucher specimens are stored in climate-controlled conditions at 21°C and 47% relative humidity. TERN samples are freely available to the Australian and international scientific communities to conduct research. To discover TERNs available samples, visit the [EcoPlots Samples](#) portal. For more information on the TERN sample use and loan process visit [EcoPlots Samples Request User Guide](#).

Datasets available include the following parameters, presented at the individual plot-based level:

- Plot location and description
- Plot vegetation community description
- Plot cover (point intercept)
- Plot vascular plant species list
- Photopoint images
- UAV imagery

² For more information on this research, see: <https://www.tern.org.au/news/news-plant-trait-research/>.

³ For more information on the *Australia's Environment* reports, see: <https://ausenv.tern.org.au/>.

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Appendix 1. Summary of TERN Plots in the Pilbara.

Plot	Property	Survey 1	Survey 2	UAV Survey	Latitude (SW corner)	Longitude (SW corner)	Broad floristic formation *
WAAPIL0001	Karijini National Park	28/04/2015	4/07/2021	29/05/2025	-22.600819	118.281503	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0002	Millstream Chichester National Park	30/04/2015	-	1/07/2025	-21.591222	117.066358	Eucalyptus low open mallee woodland
WAAPIL0003	Millstream Chichester National Park	30/08/2015	-	1/07/2025	-21.541103	117.057006	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0004	Millstream Chichester National Park	30/08/2015	24/06/2021	2/07/2025	-21.394931	117.169836	Iseilema low tussock grassland
WAAPIL0005	Millstream Chichester National Park	31/08/2015	-	1/07/2025	-21.572153	117.056264	Eucalyptus mid woodland
WAAPIL0006	Millstream Chichester National Park	1/09/2015	-	1/07/2025	-21.564244	117.059097	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0007	Water Supply Reserve	1/09/2015	-	1/07/2025	-21.677142	116.973992	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0008	Coolawanyah Station	2/09/2015	-	30/06/2025	-21.662883	117.704728	Aristida low open tussock grassland
WAAPIL0009	Coolawanyah Station	2/09/2015	-	30/06/2025	-21.872797	117.824406	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0010	Mount Florence Station	3/09/2015	-	3/06/2025	-21.857033	117.979350	Acacia tall sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0011	Mount Florence Station	4/09/2015	-	3/06/2025	-21.891925	117.999286	Acacia mid open shrubland
WAAPIL0012	Karijini National Park	5/09/2015	2/07/2021	29/05/2025	-22.620858	118.314303	Eucalyptus low open mallee woodland
WAAPIL0013	Karijini National Park	5/09/2015	1/07/2021	-	-22.610856	118.293936	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0014	Karijini National Park	6/09/2015	3/07/2021	29/05/2025	-22.635899	118.224855	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0015	Hamersley Station	6/09/2015	-	1/06/2025	-22.609278	117.935650	Iseilema low tussock grassland
WAAPIL0016	Karijini National Park	7/09/2015	-	30/05/2025	-22.723589	118.268075	Acacia low woodland
WAAPIL0017	Mulga Downs Station	8/09/2015	29/06/2021	29/06/2025	-22.133872	119.023692	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0018	Mulga Downs Station	8/09/2015	30/06/2021	28/05/2025	-22.335542	118.987772	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0019	Mulga Downs Station	9/09/2015	29/06/2021	28/05/2025	-22.302922	119.012908	Acacia tall sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0020	Millstream Chichester National Park	28/07/2016	-	2/07/2025	-21.614433	117.120475	Eucalyptus low open mallee woodland
WAAPIL0021	Millstream Chichester National Park	28/07/2016	-	2/07/2025	-21.606439	117.116136	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0022	Millstream Chichester National Park	29/07/2016	-	2/07/2025	-21.581419	117.097356	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0023	Mulga Downs Station	31/07/2016	1/07/2021	29/06/2025	-22.255000	118.695492	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0024	Marillana Station / Fortescue Marsh	1/08/2016	30/06/2021	29/06/2025	-22.467100	119.085222	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0025	Roy Hill Station	2/08/2016	25/06/2021	26/07/2025	-22.708214	119.708686	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0026	Marillana Station	2/08/2016	28/06/2021	26/07/2025	-22.766928	119.631439	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0027	Roy Hill Station	3/08/2016	26/06/2021	26/07/2025	-22.691567	119.773978	Triodia low hummock grassland
WAAPIL0028	Roy Hill Station	3/08/2016	27/06/2021	26/07/2025	-22.676553	119.840089	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0029	Roy Hill Station	4/08/2016	27/06/2021	26/07/2025	-22.661936	119.917739	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0030	RioTinto Mining Lease	5/08/2016	-	27/07/2025	-23.314739	119.632483	Santalum mid sparse shrubland

Plot	Property	Survey 1	Survey 2	UAV Survey	Latitude (SW corner)	Longitude (SW corner)	Broad floristic formation *
WAAPIL0031	RioTinto Mining Lease	6/08/2016	-	28/07/2025	-23.146047	119.265342	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0032	RioTinto Mining Lease	6/08/2016	-	28/07/2025	-23.185664	119.237931	Grevillea low open woodland
WAAPIL0033	RioTinto Mining Lease	7/08/2016	-	28/07/2025	-23.214008	119.202358	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0034	RioTinto Mining Lease	9/08/2016	-	27/07/2025	-23.301986	120.217119	Acacia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0035	BHP Mining Lease	9/08/2016	4/07/2021	-	-23.365975	120.344156	Corymbia low open woodland
WAAPIL0036	Ex-Hamersley Station	30/04/2025	-	2/06/2025	-22.341697	117.936135	Aristida low tussock grassland
WAAPIL0037	Ex-Hamersley Station	30/04/2025	-	1/06/2025	-22.392825	117.951988	Aristida low open tussock grassland
WAAPIL0038	Ex-Hamersley Station	1/05/2025	-	1/06/2025	-22.325653	117.953313	Astrebla low tussock grassland
WAAPIL0039	Ex-Hamersley Station	1/05/2025	-	2/06/2025	-22.893214	118.170200	Acacia tall sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0040	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	-	31/05/2025	-22.896731	118.188906	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0041	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	-	31/05/2025	-22.895884	118.165769	Triodia low hummock grassland
WAAPIL0042	Karijini National Park	3/05/2025	-	31/05/2025	-22.094199	115.639394	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0043	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	-	4/06/2025	-22.094993	115.652102	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0044	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	-	4/06/2025	-22.095323	115.659755	Triodia low hummock grassland
WAAPIL0045	Cane River Conservation Park	7/05/2025	-	4/06/2025	-22.095323	115.659755	Triodia low hummock grassland
WAAPIL0046	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	28/05/2025	-	23/07/2025	-21.646617	118.929361	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0047	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	29/05/2025	-	23/07/2025	-21.632897	118.962275	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0048	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	29/05/2025	-	24/07/2025	-21.670327	119.020104	Acacia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0049	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	-	23/07/2025	-21.650810	118.980749	Acacia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0050	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	-	23/07/2025	-21.653010	118.993232	Acacia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0051	Tharra/Woodstock Abydos Protected Area	30/05/2025	-	23/07/2025	-21.660458	118.998758	Acacia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0052	Purungunya Conservation Estate	1/06/2025	-	25/06/2025	-21.278976	120.456134	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0053	Purungunya Conservation Estate	1/06/2025	-	25/06/2025	-21.285658	120.431392	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0054	Purungunya Conservation Estate	2/06/2025	-	26/06/2025	-21.250608	120.460025	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0055	Purungunya Conservation Estate	2/06/2025	-	26/06/2025	-21.276231	120.596837	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0056	Purungunya Conservation Estate	3/06/2025	-	26/06/2025	-21.280449	120.598487	Triodia low sparse hummock grassland
WAAPIL0057	Purungunya Conservation Estate	3/06/2025	-	25/06/2025	-21.228694	120.452620	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0058	Purungunya Conservation Estate	4/06/2025	-	25/06/2025	-21.219525	120.480484	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0059	Eginbah Station	25/06/2025	-	26/06/2025	-21.230593	119.892457	Grevillea mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0060	Eginbah Station	25/06/2025	-	27/06/2025	-21.284798	119.952883	Triodia low hummock grassland
WAAPIL0061	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	-	27/06/2025	-21.298613	119.672488	Triodia low open hummock grassland

Plot	Property	Survey 1	Survey 2	UAV Survey	Latitude (SW corner)	Longitude (SW corner)	Broad floristic formation *
WAAPIL0062	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	-	27/06/2025	-21.288615	119.664752	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0063	Eginbah Station	26/06/2025	-	27/06/2025	-21.311803	119.654832	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0064	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	-	28/06/2025	-20.873349	119.614360	Corymbia low open woodland
WAAPIL0065	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	-	28/06/2025	-20.874239	119.620368	Triodia low sparse hummock grassland
WAAPIL0066	Eginbah Station	27/06/2025	-	28/06/2025	-20.853139	119.720241	Acacia low open woodland
WAAPIL0067	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-	-	-21.850913	120.556346	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0068	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-	-	-21.839470	120.635095	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0069	Bonney Downs Station	29/06/2025	-	-	-21.828160	120.673287	Acacia low sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0070	Bonney Downs Station	30/06/2025	-	-	-21.840425	120.645743	Eucalyptus low open woodland
WAAPIL0071	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.195136	120.023003	Acacia tall sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0072	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.220899	120.009131	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0073	Bonney Downs Station	1/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.220125	120.002199	Vachellia mid sparse shrubland
WAAPIL0074	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.214647	119.965981	Aristida low sparse tussock grassland
WAAPIL0075	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.220892	119.983646	Triodia low open hummock grassland
WAAPIL0076	Bonney Downs Station	2/07/2025	-	25/07/2025	-22.207312	119.955801	Triodia low open hummock grassland

* NVIS Level 3 description. Based on data collected during the most recent survey.

Appendix 2. Descriptions of plots surveyed in 2025

WAAPIL0001	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	28/04/2015 04/07/2021	UAV Survey	29/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.60081944	Longitude:	118.2815028 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia pruinocarpa</i> , <i>Acacia synchronicia</i> tall open shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Chrysopogon fallax</i> , <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Aristida obscura</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
04/07/2021

WAAPIL0002	Eucalyptus low open mallee woodland		
Survey	30/04/2015	UAV Survey	01/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.59122222	Longitude:	117.0663583 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus xerothermica</i> , <i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i> low open mallee woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> , <i>Codonocarpus cotinifolius</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> , <i>Heliotropium pachyphyllum</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/04/2015

WAAPIL0003		Eucalyptus low open woodland	
Survey	30/08/2015	UAV Survey	01/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.541103	Longitude:	117.057006 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia</i> , <i>Eriachne pulchella</i> subsp. <i>dominii</i> , <i>Acacia maitlandii</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/08/2015

WAAPIL0004		Iseilema low tussock grassland	
Survey	30/08/2015 24/06/2021	UAV Survey	02/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.394931	Longitude:	117.169836 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Iseilema vaginiflorum</i> , <i>Aristida latifolia</i> , <i>Cynodon convergens</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
24/06/2021

WAAPIL0005		<i>Eucalyptus</i> mid woodland	
Survey	31/08/2015	UAV Survey	01/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Floodout
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.5712389	Longitude:	117.0562583 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> subsp. <i>refulgens</i> mid woodland /Mid stratum <i>Melaleuca bracteata</i> , <i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> subsp. <i>refulgens</i> , <i>Vachellia farnesiana</i> tall shrubland /Ground stratum Cyperaceae, <i>Cyperus vaginatus</i> , <i>Themeda triandra</i> mid open sedgeland		

Representative photo

31/08/2015

WAAPIL0006		<i>Eucalyptus</i> low open woodland	
Survey	01/09/2015	UAV Survey	01/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Low hills	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.564244	Longitude:	117.059097 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> low sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia brizoides</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo

01/09/2015

WAAPIL0007		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	01/09/2015	UAV Survey	01/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Water Supply Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.677142	Longitude:	116.973992 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia trachycarpa</i> , <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>aprica</i> , <i>Acacia colei</i> var. <i>ileocarpa</i> mid open shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eulalia aurea</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
01/09/2015

WAAPIL0008		Aristida low open tussock grassland	
Survey	02/09/2015	UAV Survey	30/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial fan	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Coolawanyah Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.662883	Longitude:	117.704728 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Aristida latifolia</i> , <i>Eragrostis xerophila</i> , <i>Streptoglossa bubakii</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
02/09/2015

WAAPIL0009		Eucalyptus low open woodland	
Survey	02/09/2015	UAV Survey	30/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Floodout
Property	Coolawanyah Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.872797	Longitude:	117.824406 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. <i>oligophylla</i> , <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Melaleuca glomerata</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eriachne benthamii</i> , <i>Eulalia aurea</i> , <i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. <i>oligophylla</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
02/09/2015

WAAPIL0010		Corymbia low open woodland	
Survey	03/09/2015	UAV Survey	03/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Mount Florence Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.857033	Longitude:	117.979350 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i> , <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> , <i>Seringia nephrosperma</i> tall open shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Seringia nephrosperma</i> , <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/09/2015

WAAPIL0011	Acacia mid open shrubland		
Survey	04/09/2015	UAV Survey	03/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Mount Florence Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.891925	Longitude:	117.999286 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Acacia synchronica</i> mid open shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eragrostis xerophila</i> , <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Sclerolaena densiflora</i> low sparse tussock grassland		

Representative photo
04/09/2015

WAAPIL0012	Eucalyptus low open mallee woodland		
Survey	05/09/2015 02/07/2021	UAV Survey	29/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Hills	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.620858	Longitude:	118.314303 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus gamophylla</i> , <i>Eucalyptus pilbarensis</i> , <i>Hakea chordophylla</i> low open mallee woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia monticola</i> , <i>Acacia tenuissima</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia vanleeuwenii</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Maytenus</i> Mt Windell low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
02/07/2021

WAAPIL0014	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	06/09/2015 03/07/2021	UAV Survey	29/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.635899	Longitude:	118.224855 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Acacia pruinocarpa</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Hakea lorea</i> subsp. <i>lorea</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Aristida contorta</i> , <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Eriachne benthamii</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
03/07/2021

WAAPIL0015	Iseilema low tussock grassland		
Survey	06/09/2015	UAV Survey	01/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Low hills	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Hamersley Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.609278	Longitude:	117.935650 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Iseilema vaginiflorum</i> , <i>Cynodon convergens</i> , <i>Sida fibulifera</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
06/09/2015

WAAPIL0016	Acacia low woodland		
Survey	07/09/2015	UAV Survey	30/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Stream channel
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.723589	Longitude: 118.268075	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia citrinoviridis</i> , <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> subsp. <i>obtusa</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Cenchrus setiger</i> , <i>Themeda triandra</i> , <i>Triodia pungens</i> mid open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
07/09/2015

WAAPIL0017	Eucalyptus low open woodland		
Survey	08/09/2015 29/06/2021	UAV Survey	29/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Low hills	Landform Element	Hillcrest
Property	Mulga Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.133872	Longitude: 119.023692	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> , <i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Petalostylis labicheoides</i> , <i>Acacia monticola</i> , <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia</i> , <i>Petalostylis labicheoides</i> , <i>Tephrosia rosea</i> var. <i>Fortescue</i> creeks low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2021

WAAPIL0018		Eucalyptus low open woodland	
Survey	08/09/2015 30/06/2021	UAV Survey	28/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Floodout
Property	Mulga Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.335542	Longitude:	118.987772 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2015 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i> , <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Acacia sclerosperma</i> subsp. <i>sclerosperma</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eriachne benthamii</i> , <i>Eulalia aurea</i> , <i>Themeda triandra</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
30/06/2021

WAAPIL0019		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	09/09/2015 29/06/2021	UAV Survey	28/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Mulga Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.302922	Longitude:	119.012908 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eragrostis xerophila</i> , <i>Senna</i> , <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> low sparse tussock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2021

WAAPIL0020	<i>Eucalyptus</i> low open mallee woodland		
Survey	28/07/2016	UAV Survey	02/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.614433	Longitude:	117.120475 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus xerothermica</i> low open mallee woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> , <i>Codonocarpus cotinifolius</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
28/07/2016

WAAPIL0021	<i>Acacia</i> low open woodland		
Survey	28/07/2016	UAV Survey	02/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.606439	Longitude:	117.116136 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Acacia sclerosperma</i> subsp. <i>sclerosperma</i> , <i>Eremophila maculata</i> subsp. <i>brevifolia</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Eremophila maculata</i> subsp. <i>brevifolia</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> low open shrubland		

Representative photo
28/07/2016

WAAPIL0022	Eucalyptus low open woodland		
Survey	29/06/2016	UAV Survey	02/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Floodout
Property	Millstream Chichester National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.581419	Longitude:	117.097356 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Acacia citrinoviridis</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Eucalyptus victrix</i> , <i>Gossypium robinsonii</i> , <i>Petalostylis labicheoides</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia angusta</i> , <i>Gossypium robinsonii</i> , <i>Stylobasium spathulatum</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2016

WAAPIL0023	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	31/07/2016 01/07/2021	UAV Survey	29/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Mulga Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.255	Longitude:	118.695492 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Aristida contorta</i> , <i>Cenchrus setiger</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
01/07/2021

WAAPIL0024	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	01/08/2016 30/06/2021	UAV Survey	29/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Marillana Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.4671	Longitude:	119.085222 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Acacia pruinocarpa</i> , <i>Psyrax latifolia</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Chrysopogon fallax</i> , <i>Eulalia aurea</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
30/06/2021

WAAPIL0025	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	02/08/2016 25/06/2021	UAV Survey	26/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Roy Hill Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.708214	Longitude:	119.708686 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i> , <i>Grevillea</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Aristida contorta</i> , <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Iseilema dolichotrichum</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
25/06/2021

WAAPIL0026		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	02/08/2016 28/06/2021	UAV Survey	26/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial fan	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Marillana Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.766928	Longitude:	119.631439 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Eremophila cuneifolia</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Aristida contorta</i> , <i>Dactyloctenium radulans</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
28/06/2021

WAAPIL0027		Triodia low hummock grassland	
Survey	03/08/2016 26/06/2021	UAV Survey	26/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Roy Hill Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.691567	Longitude:	119.773978 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia angusta</i> , <i>Calandrinia stagnensis</i> , <i>Acacia synchronicia</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
26/06/2021

WAAPIL0028	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	03/08/2016 27/06/2021	UAV Survey	26/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Roy Hill Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.676553	Longitude:	119.840089 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> , <i>Acacia synchronicia</i> mid open shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Acacia xiphophylla</i> , <i>Enteropogon ramosus</i> , <i>Senna Meekatharra</i> low sparse shrubland		

Representative photo
27/06/2021

WAAPIL0029	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	04/08/2016 27/06/2021	UAV Survey	26/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Roy Hill Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.661936	Longitude:	119.917739 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2021 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Eucalyptus</i> , <i>Atalaya hemiglauca</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Eucalyptus</i> , <i>Acacia</i> , <i>Acacia sclerosperma</i> subsp. <i>sclerosperma</i> low woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia</i> , <i>Malvastrum americanum</i> , <i>Urochloa occidentalis</i> var. <i>ciliata</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
27/06/2021

WAAPIL0030 <i>Santalum</i> mid sparse shrubland			
Survey	05/08/2016	UAV Survey	27/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial fan	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Crown Land (mining) RTIO		
Plot location	Latitude: -23.314739	Longitude:	119.632483 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Santalum lanceolatum</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Aristida latifolia</i> , <i>Astrebla pectinata</i> , <i>Eragrostis xerophila</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
05/08/2016

WAAPIL0031 <i>Eucalyptus</i> low open woodland			
Survey	06/08/2016	UAV Survey	28/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Crown Land (mining) RTIO		
Plot location	Latitude: -23.146047	Longitude:	119.265342 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> , <i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i> , <i>Acacia pruinocarpa</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia pungens</i> , <i>Triodia Shovelanna Hill</i> , <i>Eriachne mucronata</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
06/08/2016

WAAPIL0032	Grevillea low open woodland		
Survey	06/08/2016	UAV Survey	28/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial fan	Landform Element	Fan
Property	Crown Land (mining) RTIO		
Plot location	Latitude: -23.185664	Longitude: 119.237931	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Grevillea berryana</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia incurvaneura</i> , <i>Grevillea berryana</i> , <i>Acacia ayersiana</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia melvillei</i> , <i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> , <i>Eremophila caespitosa</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
06/08/2016

WAAPIL0033	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	07/08/2016	UAV Survey	28/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Crown Land (mining) RTIO		
Plot location	Latitude: -23.214008	Longitude: 119.202358	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia incurvaneura</i> , <i>Eucalyptus xerothematica</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia incurvaneura</i> , <i>Corymbia deserticola</i> subsp. <i>deserticola</i> , <i>Grevillea berryana</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Aristida inaequiglumis</i> , <i>Ptilotus obovatus</i> , Poaceae low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
07/08/2016

WAAPIL0034	Acacia mid sparse shrubland		
Survey	09/08/2016	UAV Survey	27/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Sandplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Crown Land (mining) RTIO		
Plot location	Latitude: -23.301986	Longitude:	120.217119 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2016 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia melleodora</i> , <i>Hakea lorea</i> subsp. <i>lorea</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia schinzii</i> , <i>Triodia basedowii</i> , <i>Cassyltha capillaris</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
09/08/2016

WAAPIL0036	Aristida low tussock grassland		
Survey	30/04/2025	UAV Survey	02/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex. Hamersley Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.341697	Longitude:	117.936135 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Vachellia farnesiana</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Aristida latifolia</i> , <i>Chrysopogon fallax</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
30/04/2025

WAAPIL0037	<i>Aristida</i> low open tussock grassland		
Survey	30/04/2025	UAV Survey	01/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex. Hamersley Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.390066	Longitude:	117.935412 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Aristida latifolia</i> , <i>Astrebla pectinata</i> low open tussock grassland		

Representative photo
30/04/2025

WAAPIL0038	<i>Astrebla</i> low tussock grassland		
Survey	01/05/2025	UAV Survey	01/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex. Hamersley Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.392825	Longitude:	117.951988 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Vachellia farnesiana</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Astrebla pectinata</i> , <i>Chrysopogon fallax</i> low tussock grassland		

Representative photo
01/05/2025

WAAPIL0039	Acacia tall sparse shrubland		
Survey	01/05/2025	UAV Survey	02/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Unallocated Crown Land - Ex. Hamersley Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.325653	Longitude:	117.953313 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia aptaneura</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia melvillei</i> , <i>Aristida contorta</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
01/05/2025

WAAPIL0040	Triodia low open hummock grassland		
Survey	03/05/2025	UAV Survey	31/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Low hills	Landform Element	Hillcrest
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.893214	Longitude:	118.170200 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/05/2025

WAAPIL0041	Triodia low hummock grassland		
Survey	03/05/2025	UAV Survey	31/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Pediplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.896731	Longitude:	118.188906 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/05/2025

WAAPIL0042	Triodia low open hummock grassland		
Survey	03/05/2025	UAV Survey	31/05/2025
Landform Pattern	Pediplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Karijini National Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.895884	Longitude:	118.165769 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Melaleuca eleuterostachya</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/05/2025

WAAPIL0043		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	07/05/2025	UAV Survey	04/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Cane River Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.094199	Longitude:	115.639394 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia glabra</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
07/05/2025

WAAPIL0044		Triodia low hummock grassland	
Survey	07/05/2025	UAV Survey	04/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Cane River Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.094993	Longitude:	115.652102 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
07/05/2025

WAAPIL0045		Triodia low hummock grassland	
Survey	07/05/2025	UAV Survey	04/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Cane River Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.095323	Longitude:	115.659755 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia synchronicia</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia longiceps</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
07/05/2025

WAAPIL0046		Triodia low open hummock grassland	
Survey	28/05/2025	UAV Survey	23/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Karnparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.646617	Longitude:	118.929361 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia lanigera</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
28/05/2025

WAAPIL0047	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	29/05/2025	UAV Survey	23/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Karnparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.632897	Longitude:	118.962275 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Triodia longiceps</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/05/2025

WAAPIL0048	<i>Acacia</i> mid sparse shrubland		
Survey	29/05/2025	UAV Survey	24/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Karnparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.670327	Longitude:	119.020104 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> , <i>Acacia maitlandii</i> , <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia lanigera</i> , <i>Senna notabilis</i> , <i>Aristida holathera</i> var. <i>holathera</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/05/2025

WAAPIL0049		Acacia mid sparse shrubland	
Survey	30/05/2025	UAV Survey	23/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Karnparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.650810	Longitude:	118.980749 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid Stratum+ <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Acacia stellaticeps</i> , <i>Cassytha capillaris</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/05/2025

WAAPIL0050		Acacia mid sparse shrubland	
Survey	30/05/2025	UAV Survey	23/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Karnparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.653010	Longitude:	118.993232 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia orthocarpa</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/05/2025

WAAPIL0051	Acacia mid sparse shrubland		
Survey	30/05/2025	UAV Survey	23/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Tharra Kamparnmana Aboriginal Reserve		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.660458	Longitude:	118.998758 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> , <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/05/2025

WAAPIL0052	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	01/06/2025	UAV Survey	25/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Crest
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.278976	Longitude:	120.456134 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
01/06/2025

WAAPIL0053		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	02/06/2025	UAV Survey	25/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Slope
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.285658	Longitude:	120.431392 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
02/06/2025

WAAPIL0054		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	02/06/2025	UAV Survey	26/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.250608	Longitude:	120.460025 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
02/06/2025

WAAPIL0055	Acacia low open woodland		
Survey	03/06/2025	UAV Survey	26/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.276231	Longitude:	120.596837 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/06/2025

WAAPIL0056	Triodia low sparse hummock grassland		
Survey	03/06/2025	UAV Survey	26/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Slope
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.280449	Longitude:	120.598487 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Triodia brizoides</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/06/2025

WAAPIL0057	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	03/06/2025	UAV Survey	25/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Low Hills	Landform Element	Footslope
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.228694	Longitude: 120.452620	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Eriachne pulchella</i> subsp. <i>pulchella</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
03/06/2025

WAAPIL0058	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	04/06/2025	UAV Survey	25/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Low Hills	Landform Element	Hillslope
Property	Purungunya National Park and Conservation Park		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.219525	Longitude: 120.480484	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
04/06/2025

WAAPIL0059	Grevillea mid sparse shrubland		
Survey	25/06/2025	UAV Survey	26/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.230593	Longitude:	119.892457 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Mid stratum+ <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> , <i>Cajanus pubescens</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia</i> , <i>Indigofera monophylla</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
25/06/2025

WAAPIL0060	Triodia low hummock grassland		
Survey	25/06/2025	UAV Survey	27/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.284798	Longitude:	119.952883 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> , <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Aristida contorta</i> low hummock grassland		

Representative photo
25/06/2025

WAAPIL0061	Triodia low open hummock grassland		
Survey	26/06/2025	UAV Survey	27/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.298613	Longitude:	119.672488 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
26/06/2025

WAAPIL0062	Triodia low open hummock grassland		
Survey	26/06/2025	UAV Survey	27/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Slope
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.288615	Longitude:	119.664752 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
26/06/2025

WAAPIL0063		Acacia low open woodland	
Survey	26/06/2025	UAV Survey	27/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.311803	Longitude:	119.654832 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i> , <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
26/06/2025

WAAPIL0064		Corymbia low open woodland	
Survey	27/06/2025	UAV Survey	28/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Floodplain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -20.873349	Longitude:	119.614360 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Corymbia flavescens</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Acacia synchronicia</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia angusta</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
27/06/2025

WAAPIL0065	<i>Triodia</i> low sparse hummock grassland		
Survey	27/06/2025	UAV Survey	28/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Alluvial Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -20.874239	Longitude:	119.620368 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
27/06/2025

WAAPIL0066	<i>Acacia</i> low open woodland		
Survey	27/06/2025	UAV Survey	28/06/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Eginbah (Limestone) Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -20.853139	Longitude:	119.720241 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low open woodland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
27/06/2025

WAAPIL0067	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	29/06/2025	UAV Survey	N/A
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.850913	Longitude:	120.556346 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> low isolated trees /Mid stratum <i>Senna symonii</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2025

WAAPIL0068	<i>Eucalyptus</i> low open woodland		
Survey	29/06/2025	UAV Survey	N/A
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.839470	Longitude:	120.635095 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Acacia trachycarpa</i> , <i>Senna glutinosa</i> subsp. <i>x luerssenii</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2025

WAAPIL0069	Acacia low sparse shrubland		
Survey	29/06/2025	UAV Survey	N/A
Landform Pattern	Terrace	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.828160	Longitude: 120.673287	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia trachycarpa</i> , <i>Acacia bivenosa</i> low sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia longiceps</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
29/06/2025

WAAPIL0070	Eucalyptus low open woodland		
Survey	30/06/2025	UAV Survey	N/A
Landform Pattern	Pediment	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -21.840425	Longitude: 120.645743	(SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Upper stratum+ <i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i> low open woodland /Mid stratum <i>Senna glutinosa</i> subsp. x <i>luerssenii</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia brizoides</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
30/06/2025

WAAPIL0071	Acacia tall sparse shrubland		
Survey	01/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Slope
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.195136	Longitude:	120.023003 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Acacia eriopoda</i> , <i>Acacia maitlandii</i> tall sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia epactia</i> low sparse hummock grassland		

Representative photo
01/07/2025

WAAPIL0072	Triodia low open hummock grassland		
Survey	01/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.220899	Longitude:	120.009131 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> , <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i> , <i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia wiseana</i> , <i>Corchorus parviflorus</i> , <i>Senna notabilis</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
01/07/2025

WAAPIL0073	Vachellia mid sparse shrubland		
Survey	01/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.220125	Longitude:	120.002199 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Mid stratum+ <i>Vachellia farnesiana</i> , <i>Acacia glaucicaesia</i> mid sparse shrubland /Ground stratum <i>Triodia brizoides</i> , <i>Triodia longiceps</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
01/07/2025

WAAPIL0074	Aristida low sparse tussock grassland		
Survey	02/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Plain	Landform Element	Plain
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.214647	Longitude:	119.965981 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i> mid isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Aristida contorta</i> , <i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i> , <i>Sclerolaena cornishiana</i> low sparse tussock grassland		

Representative photo
02/07/2025

WAAPIL0075	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	02/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Crest
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.220892	Longitude:	119.983646 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>aprica</i> , <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> tall isolated shrubs /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> , <i>Triodia wiseana</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
02/07/2025

WAAPIL0076	<i>Triodia</i> low open hummock grassland		
Survey	02/07/2025	UAV Survey	25/07/2025
Landform Pattern	Rises	Landform Element	Slope
Property	Bonney Downs Station		
Plot location	Latitude: -22.207312	Longitude:	119.955801 (SW corner)
Vegetation community 2025 description	Emergent stratum <i>Acacia inaequilatera</i> low isolated trees /Ground stratum+ <i>Triodia epactia</i> low open hummock grassland		

Representative photo
02/07/2025

Appendix 3. Combined species list for the four years of sampling (2025, 2021, 2016 & 2015)

This table includes WA priority listed taxa, introduced status, family and common names. Taxonomy largely follows the Australian Plant Census (APC) and for the purpose of WAVE, follows Florabase, the authoritative, dynamic online resource for WA plant taxonomy (Census of Western Australian Plants; Florabase, 2026). *denotes Alien to WA, ^{P1} Priority 1, ^{P2} Priority 2, ^{P3} Priority 3, ^{P4} Priority 4.

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i>	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Abutilon amplum</i>	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Abutilon cryptopetalum</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Abutilon cunninghamii</i>	Malvaceae		2021 2015
<i>Abutilon fraseri</i>	Malvaceae	Lantern Bush	2021 2016 2015
<i>Abutilon lepidum</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Abutilon leucopetalum</i>	Malvaceae	Desert Chinese Lantern	2025 2016
<i>Abutilon macrum</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Abutilon malvifolium</i>	Malvaceae	Bastard Marshmallow	2025 2021
<i>Abutilon otocarpum</i>	Malvaceae	Desert Chinese Lantern	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Abutilon oxycarpum</i>	Malvaceae	Flannel Weed	2016
<i>Abutilon oxycarpum</i> subsp. <i>Prostrate</i> (A.A. Mitchell PRP 1266)	Malvaceae		2025 2015
<i>Abutilon</i> sp. <i>Dioicum</i> (A.A. Mitchell PRP 1618)	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Abutilon</i> sp. <i>Pilbara</i> (W.R. Barker 2025)	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Acacia adoxa</i> var. <i>adoxo</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Acacia ampliceps</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Acacia ancistrocarpa</i>	Fabaceae	Fitzroy Wattle	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia aneura</i>	Fabaceae	Mulga	2016
^{P1} <i>Acacia aphanoclada</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia aptaneura</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia arida</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia atkinsiana</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Acacia ayersiana</i>	Fabaceae		2016 2015
<i>Acacia bivenosa</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia citrinoviridis</i>	Fabaceae		2016 2015
<i>Acacia colei</i>	Fabaceae		2016 2015
<i>Acacia colei</i> var. <i>ileocarpa</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Acacia coriacea</i> subsp. <i>pendens</i>	Fabaceae		2016 2015
<i>Acacia cowleana</i>	Fabaceae	Halls Creek Wattle	2015
<i>Acacia dictyophleba</i>	Fabaceae	Sandhill Wattle	2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia distans</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Acacia eriopoda</i>	Fabaceae	Broome Pindan Wattle	2025
<i>Acacia exigua</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia glaucicaesia</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia hamersleyensis</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Acacia hilliana</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Acacia inaequilatera</i>	Fabaceae	Baderi	2025 2015
<i>Acacia incurvaneura</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Acacia ligulata</i>	Fabaceae	Umbrella Bush	2015
<i>Acacia macraneura</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Acacia maitlandii</i>	Fabaceae	Maitland's Wattle	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia marramamba</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Acacia melleodora</i>	Fabaceae		2016

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Acacia minyura</i>	Fabaceae		2021
<i>Acacia monticola</i>	Fabaceae	Gawar	2021 2015
<i>Acacia orthocarpa</i>	Fabaceae	Needleleaf Wattle	2025
<i>Acacia pachyacra</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia pruinocarpa</i>	Fabaceae	Gidgee	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia ptychophylla</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia pyrifolia</i>	Fabaceae	Ranji Bush	2015
<i>Acacia pyrifolia</i> var. <i>morrisonii</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Acacia pyrifolia</i> var. <i>pyrifolia</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia sclerosperma</i> subsp. <i>sclerosperma</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia stellaticeps</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia synchronicia</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia tenuissima</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Acacia tetragonophylla</i>	Fabaceae	Kurara	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Acacia trachycarpa</i>	Fabaceae	Minni Ritchi	2025 2016 2015
<i>Acacia trachycarpa</i> x <i>Acacia tumida</i> var. <i>pilbarensis</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Acacia tumida</i> var. <i>pilbarensis</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Acacia xiphophylla</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Chaff Flower	2015
* <i>Aerva javanica</i>	Amaranthaceae	Kapok Bush	2025 2021 2016
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	Fabaceae	Budda Pea	2015
<i>Afrohybanthus aurantiacus</i>	Violaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Alternanthera angustifolia</i>	Amaranthaceae		2021
<i>Alternanthera nana</i>	Amaranthaceae	Hairy Joyweed	2021 2016 2015
<i>Alysicarpus muelleri</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Amaranthus cuspidifolius</i>	Amaranthaceae		2015
<i>Amphipogon caricinus</i> var. <i>caricinus</i>	Poaceae		2016
<i>Amphipogon sericeus</i>	Poaceae		2015
<i>Amyema fitzgeraldii</i>	Loranthaceae	Pincushion Mistletoe	2021 2016 2015
<i>Amyema gibberula</i> var. <i>gibberula</i>	Loranthaceae		2016
<i>Amyema hilliana</i>	Loranthaceae		2015
<i>Androcalva luteiflora</i>	Malvaceae	Yellow-flowered Rulingia	2015
<i>Anthobolus leptomerioides</i>	Santalaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Areocleome oxalidea</i>	Cleomaceae		2016
<i>Aristida contorta</i>	Poaceae	Bunched Kerosene Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Aristida holathera</i> var. <i>holathera</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Aristida inaequiglumis</i>	Poaceae	Feathertop Threeawn	2025 2021 2016 2015
^{P3} <i>Aristida jerichoensis</i> var. <i>subspinulifera</i>	Poaceae		2021 2015
<i>Aristida latifolia</i>	Poaceae	Feathertop Wiregrass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Aristida nitidula</i>	Poaceae	Flat-awned Threeawn	2025
<i>Aristida obscura</i>	Poaceae	Brush Threeawn	2021 2016 2015
<i>Arivela uncifera</i>	Cleomaceae		2025
<i>Arivela viscosa</i>	Cleomaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Astrelba elymoides</i>	Poaceae	Weeping Mitchell Grass	2025 2015
<i>Astrelba pectinata</i>	Poaceae	Barley Mitchell Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Atalaya hemiglauca</i>	Sapindaceae	Whitewood	2021 2016 2015
<i>Atriplex amnicola</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Swamp Saltbush	2025
<i>Atriplex codonocarpa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Flat-topped Saltbush	2016 2015
<i>Austrobryonia pilbarensis</i>	Cucurbitaceae		2016 2015
<i>Bergia pedicellaris</i>	Elatinaceae		2015

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* <i>Bidens bipinnata</i>	Asteraceae	Bipinnate Beggartick	2021
* <i>Bidens pilosa</i>	Asteraceae	Cobbler's Pegs	2021
<i>Blumea tenella</i>	Asteraceae		2021 2015
<i>Boerhavia coccinea</i>	Nyctaginaceae	Tar Vine	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Boerhavia gardneri</i>	Nyctaginaceae		2025
<i>Boerhavia paludosa</i>	Nyctaginaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Boerhavia schomburgkiana</i>	Nyctaginaceae		2016
<i>Bonamia alatisemina</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025
<i>Bonamia erecta</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Bonamia linearis</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025
<i>Bonamia pannosa</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025
<i>Bonamia pilbarensis</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Bothriochloa ewartiana</i>	Poaceae	Desert Bluegrass	2025
<i>Brachyscome iberidifolia</i>	Asteraceae	Swan River Daisy	2021
<i>Bulbine pendula</i>	Asphodelaceae		2016
<i>Bulbostylis barbata</i>	Cyperaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Bulbostylis turbinata</i>	Cyperaceae		2015
<i>Cajanus pubescens</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Calandrinia ptychosperma</i>	Portulacaceae		2015
<i>Calandrinia pumila</i>	Portulacaceae		2015
<i>Calandrinia stagnensis</i>	Portulacaceae		2021 2016
<i>Calocephalus beardii</i>	Asteraceae		2016 2015
<i>Calocephalus pilbarensis</i>	Asteraceae		2016 2015
<i>Calotis hispidula</i>	Asteraceae	Bindy Eye	2016
<i>Calotis plumulifera</i>	Asteraceae		2016 2015
<i>Capparis lasiantha</i>	Capparaceae	Split Jack	2021 2016 2015
<i>Capparis spinosa</i> subsp. <i>nummularia</i>	Capparaceae	Coastal Caper	2021 2016 2015
<i>Capparis umbonata</i>	Capparaceae	Wild Orange	2021 2016 2015
<i>Carissa lanceolata</i>	Apocynaceae	Conkerberry	2025 2016
<i>Cassytha capillaris</i>	Lauraceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Cassytha filiformis</i>	Lauraceae	Love Vine	2015
* <i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i>	Poaceae	Buffel Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
* <i>Cenchrus setiger</i>	Poaceae	Birdwood Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Centipeda minima</i> subsp. <i>macrocephala</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Cheilanthes sieberi</i> subsp. <i>sieberi</i>	Pteridaceae	Mulga Fern	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Chloris pectinata</i>	Poaceae	Comb Chloris	2021 2015
<i>Chrysocephalum gilesii</i>	Asteraceae		2021 2015
<i>Chrysopogon fallax</i>	Poaceae	Golden Beard Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
^{P2} <i>Cladium procerum</i>	Cyperaceae		2015
<i>Clerodendrum floribundum</i> var. <i>angustifolium</i>	Lamiaceae		2021 2015
<i>Codonocarpus cotinifolius</i>	Gyrostemonaceae	Native Poplar	2025 2016 2015
<i>Convolvulus clementii</i>	Convolvulaceae		2016 2015
<i>Corchorus crozophorifolius</i>	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Corchorus elachocarpus</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Corchorus laniflorus</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Corchorus lasiocarpus</i> subsp. <i>lasiocarpus</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Corchorus lasiocarpus</i> subsp. <i>parvus</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Corchorus parviflorus</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Corchorus sidoides</i> subsp. <i>sidoides</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Corchorus sidoides</i> subsp. <i>vermicularis</i>	Malvaceae		2016

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Corchorus tectus</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Corchorus tridens</i>	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Corchorus trilocularis</i>	Malvaceae		2021 2015
<i>Corchorus walcottii</i>	Malvaceae	Woolly Corchorus	2025
<i>Corymbia deserticola</i> subsp. <i>deserticola</i>	Myrtaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Corymbia ferriticola</i>	Myrtaceae		2025
<i>Corymbia flavescens</i>	Myrtaceae		2025
<i>Corymbia hamersleyana</i>	Myrtaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Crotalaria dissitiflora</i> subsp. <i>benthamiana</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2015
* <i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	Fabaceae	Sunnhemp	2021 2015
<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> var. <i>neglecta</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Cucumis argenteus</i>	Cucurbitaceae		2025
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Ulcardo Melon	2015
<i>Cucumis picrocarpus</i>	Cucurbitaceae		2021 2015
<i>Cucumis variabilis</i>	Cucurbitaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Cullen cinereum</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Cullen graveolens</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Cullen lachnostachys</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Cullen leucanthum</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Cullen leucochaites</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Cullen martinii</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Cullen pogonocarpum</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Cullen stipulaceum</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Cymbopogon ambiguus</i>	Poaceae	Scentgrass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Cymbopogon obtectus</i>	Poaceae	Silkyheads	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Cynodon convergens</i>	Poaceae	Spider Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
* <i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Poaceae	Couch	2015
<i>Cynodon prostratus</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Cynodon tenellus</i>	Poaceae	Slender Native Couch	2025
<i>Cyperus cunninghamii</i> subsp. <i>cunninghamii</i>	Cyperaceae		2015
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Cyperaceae	Rice Sedge	2015
<i>Cyperus vaginatus</i>	Cyperaceae	Stiffleaf Sedge	2015
<i>Dactyloctenium radulans</i>	Poaceae	Button Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Dampiera candidans</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Dendrophyllanthus erwinii</i>	Phyllanthaceae		2025 2015
<i>Desmodiopsis campylocaulon</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2016
<i>Dichanthium fecundum</i>	Poaceae	Curly Bluegrass	2025
<i>Dichanthium sericeum</i> subsp. <i>humilius</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Dichanthium sericeum</i> subsp. <i>polystachyum</i>	Poaceae		2021 2015
<i>Dichanthium sericeum</i> subsp. <i>sericeum</i>	Poaceae		2016
<i>Dicladantha forrestii</i>	Acanthaceae		2015
<i>Dicrastylis cordifolia</i>	Lamiaceae		2016
<i>Digitaria ammophila</i>	Poaceae	Silky Umbrella Grass	2021
<i>Digitaria brownii</i>	Poaceae	Cotton Panic Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Digitaria ctenantha</i>	Poaceae	Comb Finger Grass	2021
<i>Digitaria papposa</i>	Poaceae		2021
<i>Diplopeltis eriocarpa</i>	Sapindaceae	Hairy Pepperflower	2016
<i>Diplopeltis stuartii</i> var. <i>stuartii</i>	Sapindaceae	Desert Pepperflower	2016
<i>Dipteracanthus australasicus</i> subsp. <i>australasicus</i>	Acanthaceae		2016
<i>Dissocarpus paradoxus</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Curious Saltbush	2025

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<i>Dodonaea coriacea</i>	Sapindaceae		2016 2015
<i>Dodonaea lanceolata</i> var. <i>lanceolata</i>	Sapindaceae		2016 2015
<i>Dodonaea pachyneura</i>	Sapindaceae		2015
<i>Dodonaea petiolaris</i>	Sapindaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> subsp. <i>mucronata</i>	Sapindaceae		2015
<i>Dolichocarpa crouchiana</i>	Rubiaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Duperreya commixta</i>	Convolvulaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Dysphania glomulifera</i> subsp. <i>eremaea</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2021
<i>Dysphania kalpari</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Rat's Tail	2021 2015
<i>Dysphania melanocarpa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Black Crumbweed	2016
<i>Dysphania rhadinostachya</i> subsp. <i>inflata</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2015
<i>Dysphania rhadinostachya</i> subsp. <i>rhadinostachya</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2021 2016 2015
* <i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Poaceae	Awnless Barnyard Grass	2015
<i>Ehretia saligna</i> var. <i>saligna</i>	Boraginaceae		2021 2015
<i>Elytrophorus spicatus</i>	Poaceae	Spikegrass	2015
<i>Enchylaena tomentosa</i> var. <i>tomentosa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Barrier Saltbush	2021 2016 2015
<i>Enneapogon avenaceus</i>	Poaceae	Bottle Washers	2025
<i>Enneapogon caeruleus</i>	Poaceae	Limestone Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Enneapogon lindleyanus</i>	Poaceae	Wiry Nineawn	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Enneapogon polyphyllus</i>	Poaceae	Leafy Nineawn	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Enneapogon purpurascens</i>	Poaceae	Purple Nineawn	2025
<i>Enneapogon robustissimus</i>	Poaceae		2021 2015
<i>Enteropogon ramosus</i>	Poaceae	Windmill Grass	2021 2016 2015
<i>Eragrostis cumingii</i>	Poaceae	Cuming's Love Grass	2025 2021 2015
<i>Eragrostis desertorum</i>	Poaceae	Desert Lovegrass	2025 2016
<i>Eragrostis dielsii</i>	Poaceae	Mallee Lovegrass	2021 2016 2015
<i>Eragrostis elongata</i>	Poaceae	Clustered Lovegrass	2015
<i>Eragrostis eriopoda</i>	Poaceae	Woollybutt Grass	2025 2021 2016
<i>Eragrostis leptocarpa</i>	Poaceae	Drooping Lovegrass	2021
<i>Eragrostis pergracilis</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eragrostis setifolia</i>	Poaceae	Neverfail Grass	2015
<i>Eragrostis tenellula</i>	Poaceae	Delicate Lovegrass	2025 2021 2015
<i>Eragrostis xerophila</i>	Poaceae	Knotty-butt Neverfail	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila caespitosa</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Felty-leaved Eremophila	2016
<i>Eremophila cuneifolia</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Pinyuru	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila exilifolia</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2025
<i>Eremophila flaccida</i> subsp. <i>flaccida</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2015
<i>Eremophila forrestii</i> subsp. <i>forrestii</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila jucunda</i> subsp. <i>pulcherrima</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2021 2015
<i>Eremophila lanceolata</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila latrobei</i> subsp. <i>filiformis</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila latrobei</i> subsp. <i>latrobei</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Native Fuschia	2021
<i>Eremophila longifolia</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Berrigan	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eremophila maculata</i> subsp. <i>brevifolia</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Native Fuchsia	2016
^{P4} <i>Eremophila magnifica</i> subsp. <i>magnifica</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2015
^{P4} <i>Eremophila youngii</i> subsp. <i>lepidota</i>	Scrophulariaceae		2021 2016
<i>Eriachne aristidea</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eriachne benthamii</i>	Poaceae	Swamp Wanderrie	2021 2016 2015
<i>Eriachne flaccida</i>	Poaceae	Claypan Grass	2025 2016
<i>Eriachne lanata</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2015

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<i>Eriachne mucronata</i>	Poaceae	Mountain Wanderie Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eriachne pulchella</i> subsp. <i>dominii</i>	Poaceae		2025 2015
<i>Eriachne pulchella</i> subsp. <i>pulchella</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> subsp. <i>obtusata</i>	Myrtaceae	Blunt-budded River Red Gum	2015
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> subsp. <i>refulgens</i>	Myrtaceae		2015
<i>Eucalyptus gamophylla</i>	Myrtaceae	Twin-leaf Mallee	2021 2016 2015
<i>Eucalyptus leucophloia</i> subsp. <i>leucophloia</i>	Myrtaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Eucalyptus pilbarensis</i>	Myrtaceae		2021
<i>Eucalyptus trivalva</i>	Myrtaceae	Victoria Spring Mallee	2015
<i>Eucalyptus victrix</i>	Myrtaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Eucalyptus xerothermica</i>	Myrtaceae		2016 2015
<i>Eulalia aurea</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Euphorbia australis</i> var. <i>subtomentosa</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2025 2015
<i>Euphorbia biconvexa</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Euphorbia boophthona</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Gascoyne Spurge	2015
<i>Euphorbia careyi</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2025
<i>Euphorbia coghlanii</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Namana	2025 2016 2015
<i>Euphorbia drummondii</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Caustic Weed	2021 2015
<i>Euphorbia ferdinandi</i> var. <i>appendiculata</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2021
<i>Euphorbia ferdinandi</i> var. <i>ferdinandi</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2025
^{P3} <i>Euphorbia stevenii</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Caustic Bottle tree	2015
<i>Euphorbia tannensis</i> subsp. <i>eremophila</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Desert Spurge	2025 2021 2016
<i>Euphorbia trigonosperma</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2015
<i>Euphorbia vaccaria</i> var. <i>erucoides</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2015
<i>Euphorbia vaccaria</i> var. <i>vaccaria</i>	Euphorbiaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Euploca chrysocarpa</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Euploca conocarpa</i>	Boraginaceae		2015
<i>Euploca cunninghamii</i>	Boraginaceae		2025
<i>Euploca glandulifera</i>	Boraginaceae		2016
<i>Euploca heterantha</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Euploca inexplicita</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Euploca ovalifolia</i>	Boraginaceae		2025
<i>Euploca pachyphylla</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2015
<i>Euploca skeleton</i>	Boraginaceae		2025
<i>Euploca tanythrix</i>	Boraginaceae		2025
<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> var. <i>villosicalyx</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i>	Cyperaceae	Eight Day Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Fimbristylis simulans</i>	Cyperaceae		2025 2015
<i>Flaveria australasica</i> subsp. <i>gilgai</i>	Asteraceae		2015
* <i>Flaveria trinervia</i>	Asteraceae	Speedy Weed	2021 2015
<i>Frankenia setosa</i>	Frankeniaceae	Bristly Frankenia	2016
<i>Glycine canescens</i>	Fabaceae	Silky Glycine	2016 2015
<i>Gnephosis brevifolia</i>	Asteraceae	Short-leaved Gnephosis	2016
<i>Gompholobium oreophilum</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Gomphrena affinis</i> subsp. <i>pilbarensis</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Gomphrena canescens</i> subsp. <i>canescens</i>	Amaranthaceae		2021
<i>Gomphrena cunninghamii</i>	Amaranthaceae		2015
<i>Gomphrena kanisii</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Gomphrena leptoclada</i> subsp. <i>leptoclada</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025
<i>Goodenia connata</i>	Goodeniaceae	Cup Velleia	2015

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<i>Goodenia cusackiana</i>	Goodeniaceae		2021 2015
<i>Goodenia forrestii</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2016
<i>Goodenia lamprosperma</i>	Goodeniaceae		2015
<i>Goodenia microptera</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Goodenia muelleriana</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Goodenia nuda</i>	Goodeniaceae		2021 2016 2015
^{P3} <i>Goodenia obscurata</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025
<i>Goodenia pascua</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Goodenia prostrata</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Goodenia stobbsiana</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Goodenia triodiophila</i>	Goodeniaceae		2016 2015
<i>Goodenia vilmorinae</i>	Goodeniaceae		2021 2016
<i>Gossypium australe</i>	Malvaceae	Native Cotton	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Gossypium robinsonii</i>	Malvaceae	Wild Cotton	2021 2016 2015
<i>Grevillea berryana</i>	Proteaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Grevillea juncifolia</i> subsp. <i>juncifolia</i>	Proteaceae		2016
<i>Grevillea pyramidalis</i> subsp. <i>leucadendron</i>	Proteaceae		2025
<i>Grevillea striata</i>	Proteaceae	Beefwood	2021 2016
<i>Grevillea wickhamii</i>	Proteaceae	Wickham's Grevillea	2016
<i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>aprica</i>	Proteaceae		2025 2015
<i>Grevillea wickhamii</i> subsp. <i>hispidula</i>	Proteaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Grona muelleri</i>	Fabaceae		2021 2015
<i>Hakea chordophylla</i>	Proteaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Hakea lorea</i> subsp. <i>lorea</i>	Proteaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Halgania solanacea</i> var. <i>Mt Doreen</i> (G.M. Chippendale 4206)	Boraginaceae		2016
<i>Haloragis gossei</i> var. <i>gossei</i>	Haloragaceae		2015
<i>Haloragis maierae</i>	Haloragaceae		2015
<i>Haloragis trigonocarpa</i>	Haloragaceae		2015
<i>Heliotropium crispatum</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Hibiscus austrinus</i> var. <i>austrinus</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Hibiscus brachychlaenus</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Hibiscus brachysiphonius</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2015
<i>Hibiscus burtonii</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Hibiscus coatesii</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Hibiscus leptocladus</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Hibiscus sturtii</i> var. <i>campylochlamys</i>	Malvaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Hibiscus sturtii</i> var. <i>platychlamys</i>	Malvaceae		2021
<i>Hibiscus verdcourtii</i>	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Indigofera colutea</i>	Fabaceae	Sticky Indigo	2025 2021
<i>Indigofera deserticola</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Indigofera georgei</i>	Fabaceae	Bovine Indigo	2021 2016
<i>Indigofera linifolia</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Indigofera linnaei</i>	Fabaceae	Birdsville Indigo	2025
<i>Indigofera monophylla</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Indigofera rivularis</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Indigofera rugosa</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Indigofera trita</i> subsp. <i>trita</i>	Fabaceae		2021
<i>Ipomoea lonchophylla</i>	Convolvulaceae	Cowvine	2025
<i>Ipomoea muelleri</i>	Convolvulaceae	Poison Morning Glory	2025 2021 2015
<i>Ipomoea plebeia</i>	Convolvulaceae	Bellvine	2015

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Iseilema dolichotrichum</i>	Poaceae		2021 2015
<i>Iseilema membranaceum</i>	Poaceae	Small Flinders Grass	2021 2016 2015
<i>Iseilema vaginiflorum</i>	Poaceae	Red Flinders Grass	2025 2021 2015
<i>Isotropis atropurpurea</i>	Fabaceae	Poison Sage	2021 2015
^{P2} <i>Isotropis forrestii</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Isotropis iophyta</i>	Fabaceae	Eremaean Lamb's Poison	2021
<i>Jacksonia aculeata</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Jacquemontia distigma</i>	Convolvulaceae		2015
<i>Jasminum didymum</i> subsp. <i>lineare</i>	Oleaceae	Desert Jasmine	2021 2015
<i>Kennedia prorepens</i>	Fabaceae		2016
* <i>Lactuca serriola</i>	Asteraceae	Prickly Lettuce	2015
<i>Lawrencia densiflora</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Leichhardtia australis</i>	Apocynaceae	Cogola Bush	2021
<i>Leiocarpa semicalva</i>	Asteraceae		2016
<i>Lepidium muelleri-ferdinandi</i>	Brassicaceae		2016 2015
<i>Lepidium oxytrichum</i>	Brassicaceae		2016
<i>Lepidium phlebopetalum</i>	Brassicaceae	Veined Peppergrass	2016 2015
<i>Lepidium pholidogynum</i>	Brassicaceae		2025
<i>Lepidium platypetalum</i>	Brassicaceae	Slender Peppergrass	2025
<i>Leptosema chambersii</i>	Fabaceae		2016
^{P4} <i>Livistona alfredii</i>	Arecaceae	Millstream Fan-palm	2016 2015
<i>Lobelia heterophylla</i> subsp. <i>pilbarensis</i>	Campanulaceae		2015
<i>Lotus cruentus</i>	Fabaceae	Redflower Lotus	2015
<i>Maireana carnososa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Cottony Bluebush	2021 2016
<i>Maireana georgei</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Satiny Bluebush	2021 2016
<i>Maireana melanocoma</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Pussy Bluebush	2021 2016 2015
<i>Maireana planifolia</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Low Bluebush	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Maireana tomentosa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Felty Bluebush	2025 2021 2016
<i>Maireana triptera</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Threewinged Bluebush	2021 2016
<i>Maireana villosa</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2021 2016 2015
* <i>Malvastrum americanum</i>	Malvaceae	Spiked Malvastrum	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Marsilea hirsuta</i>	Marsileaceae	Nardoo	2025 2015
<i>Maytenus</i> sp. Mt Windell (S. van Leeuwen 846)	Celastraceae		2021 2015
<i>Melaleuca argentea</i>	Myrtaceae	Silver Cadjeput	2015
<i>Melaleuca bracteata</i>	Myrtaceae	River Teatree	2015
<i>Melaleuca eleuterostachya</i>	Myrtaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Melaleuca glomerata</i>	Myrtaceae		2015
<i>Melhanian oblongifolia</i>	Malvaceae		2016 2015
<i>Menkea villosula</i>	Brassicaceae		2016
<i>Mimulus gracilis</i>	Phrymaceae		2015
<i>Minuria integerrima</i>	Asteraceae	Smooth Minuria	2025 2016
<i>Mirbelia ramulosa</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Nellica maderaspatensis</i>	Phyllanthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Neptunia dimorphantha</i>	Fabaceae	Sensitive Plant	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Neptunia scutata</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Neptunia xanthonema</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Neurachne muelleri</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Newcastelia cladotricha</i>	Lamiaceae	Lambs Tail	2016
<i>Nicotiana occidentalis</i>	Solanaceae	Native Tobacco	2016
<i>Nicotiana rosulata</i>	Solanaceae		2015

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Nicotiana simulans</i>	Solanaceae		2016 2015
<i>Notoleptopus decaisnei</i>	Phyllanthaceae		2015
<i>Operculina aequisejala</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Panicum australiense</i> var. <i>australiense</i>	Poaceae		2025 2015
<i>Panicum decompositum</i>	Poaceae	Native Millet	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Panicum effusum</i>	Poaceae	Hairy Panic Grass	2015
<i>Panicum laevinode</i>	Poaceae		2021 2015
<i>Paspalidium clementii</i>	Poaceae	Clements Paspalidium	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Paspalidium constrictum</i>	Poaceae	Knottybutt Grass	2025
<i>Paspalidium rarum</i>	Poaceae	Rare Paspalidium	2021 2015
* <i>Passiflora foetida</i> var. <i>hispida</i>	Passifloraceae		2015
<i>Peplidium aithocheilum</i>	Phrymaceae		2021
<i>Peplidium</i> sp. C Evol. Fl. Fauna Arid Aust. (N.T. Burbidge & A. Kanis 8158)	Phrymaceae		2016
<i>Peripleura arida</i>	Asteraceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Peripleura obovata</i>	Asteraceae		2021
<i>Peripleura virgata</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Perotis rara</i>	Poaceae	Comet Grass	2021 2016 2015
<i>Petalostylis cassioides</i>	Fabaceae		2016
<i>Petalostylis labicheoides</i>	Fabaceae	Slender Petalostylis	2021 2016 2015
* <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Arecaceae	Date Palm	2015
<i>Pimelea ammocharis</i>	Thymelaeaceae		2016 2015
<i>Pluchea dentex</i>	Asteraceae		2025 2015
<i>Pluchea dunlopia</i>	Asteraceae		2016
<i>Pluchea ferdinandi-muelleri</i>	Asteraceae		2025
<i>Pluchea rubelliflora</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Pluchea tetranthera</i>	Asteraceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i>	Caryophyllaceae		2021 2015
<i>Polycarpaea holtzei</i>	Caryophyllaceae		2025 2015
<i>Polycarpaea longiflora</i>	Caryophyllaceae		2025 2015
<i>Polygala glaucifolia</i>	Polygalaceae		2025 2015
<i>Polygala isingii</i>	Polygalaceae		2016 2015
<i>Polymeria ambigua</i>	Convolvulaceae	Morning Glory	2025 2021
<i>Polymeria longifolia</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025
<i>Polymeria mollis</i>	Convolvulaceae		2025
<i>Portulaca decipiens</i>	Portulacaceae		2025
<i>Portulaca filifolia</i>	Portulacaceae		2025 2021
<i>Portulaca intraterranea</i>	Portulacaceae		2015
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Portulacaceae	Purslane	2025 2021 2016 2015
* <i>Portulaca pilosa</i>	Portulacaceae	Djanggarra	2015
* <i>Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum</i>	Asteraceae	Jersey Cudweed	2015
<i>Psyrax latifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Native Plum	2021 2016 2015
<i>Psyrax suaveolens</i>	Rubiaceae		2021
<i>Pterocaulon sphacelatum</i>	Asteraceae	Apple Bush	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus aevoides</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus astrolasius</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus auriculifolius</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2015
<i>Ptilotus axillaris</i>	Amaranthaceae	Mat Mulla Mulla	2025 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus calostachyus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Weeping Mulla Mulla	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus carinatus</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Ptilotus clementii</i>	Amaranthaceae	Tassel Top	2025 2021 2015

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Ptilotus exaltatus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Tall Mulla Mulla	2025 2021
<i>Ptilotus fusiformis</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Ptilotus gaudichaudii</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus gomphrenoides</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus helipteroides</i>	Amaranthaceae	Hairy Mulla Mulla	2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus incanus</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025
<i>Ptilotus murrayi</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025
<i>Ptilotus nobilis</i>	Amaranthaceae	Tall Mulla Mulla	2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus obovatus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Cotton Bush	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus polystachyus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Prince of Wales Feather	2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus roei</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025 2016
<i>Ptilotus rotundifolius</i>	Amaranthaceae	Royal Mulla Mulla	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Ptilotus schwartzii</i> var. <i>schwartzii</i>	Amaranthaceae		2025
<i>Rhagodia eremaea</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Thorny Saltbush	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Rhagodia</i> sp. Hamersley (M. Trudgen 17794)	Chenopodiaceae		2016
<i>Rhodanthe floribunda</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Rhodanthe margarethae</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Rhynchosia australis</i>	Fabaceae	Rhynchosia	2025
<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Fabaceae	Rhynchosia	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Roebuckiella similis</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Roepera eichleri</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Roepera similis</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2016
<i>Rostellularia adscendens</i> var. <i>clementii</i>	Acanthaceae		2021 2015
* <i>Rumex vesicarius</i>	Polygonaceae	Ruby Dock	2015
<i>Salsola australis</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Santalum lanceolatum</i>	Santalaceae	Northern Sandalwood	2021 2016 2015
<i>Santalum spicatum</i>	Santalaceae	Sandalwood	2021
<i>Scaevola acacioides</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025
<i>Scaevola amblyanthera</i> var. <i>centralis</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025
<i>Scaevola browniana</i> subsp. <i>browniana</i>	Goodeniaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Scaevola parvifolia</i> subsp. <i>pilbarae</i>	Goodeniaceae		2016 2015
<i>Scaevola spinescens</i>	Goodeniaceae	Currant Bush	2021 2016
<i>Schenkia clementii</i>	Gentianaceae		2015
<i>Schizachyrium fragile</i>	Poaceae	Senale Redgrass	2021
<i>Sclerolaena bicornis</i> var. <i>bicornis</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Goathead Burr	2015
<i>Sclerolaena cornishiana</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Cartwheel Burr	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Sclerolaena costata</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Sclerolaena cuneata</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Yellow Bindii	2021 2016 2015
<i>Sclerolaena densiflora</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Sclerolaena deserticola</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2016
<i>Sclerolaena diacantha</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Grey Copperburr	2021
<i>Sclerolaena eriacantha</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Tall Bindii	2025 2021
<i>Sclerolaena hostilis</i>	Chenopodiaceae		2025
<i>Sclerolaena lanicuspis</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Spinach Burr	2016 2015
<i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. <i>helmsii</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. <i>oligophylla</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. <i>x petiolaris</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Senna ferraria</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Senna glaucifolia</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Senna glutinosa</i> subsp. <i>glutinosa</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Senna glutinosa</i> subsp. <i>pruinosa</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Senna glutinosa</i> subsp. <i>x luerssenii</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Senna hamersleyensis</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Senna notabilis</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Senna pleurocarpa</i> var. <i>angustifolia</i>	Fabaceae		2021
^{P3} <i>Senna</i> sp. Barlee Range (S. van Leeuwen 1520)	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Senna</i> sp. Meekatharra (E. Bailey 1-26)	Fabaceae		2021 2016
<i>Senna symonii</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Senna venusta</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Seringia exastia</i>	Malvaceae	Fringed fire-bush	2021 2015
<i>Seringia nephrosperma</i>	Malvaceae	Free carpel fire-bush	2016
<i>Sesbania cannabina</i>	Fabaceae	Sesbania Pea	2015
<i>Setaria dielsii</i>	Poaceae	Diels' Pigeon Grass	2016 2015
* <i>Setaria verticillata</i>	Poaceae	Whorled Pigeon Grass	2021 2016 2015
<i>Sida arenicola</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Sida arsinata</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Sida cardiophylla</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Sida clementii</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Sida echinocarpa</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Sida ectogama</i>	Malvaceae		2016
<i>Sida fibulifera</i>	Malvaceae	Silver Sida	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Sida platycalyx</i>	Malvaceae	Lifesaver Burr	2025 2021 2016
<i>Sida rohlenae</i> subsp. <i>rohlenae</i>	Malvaceae		2025 2016
<i>Sida</i> sp. Articulation below (A.A.Mitchell PRP1605)	Malvaceae		2021
^{P4} <i>Sida</i> sp. Barlee Range (S. van Leeuwen 1642)	Malvaceae		2021
<i>Sida</i> sp. Excedentifolia (J.L. Egan 1925)	Malvaceae		2021 2015
<i>Sida</i> sp. Golden calyces glabrous fruit (H.N.Foote)	Malvaceae		2016
^{P3} <i>Sida</i> sp. Hamersley Range (K. Newbey 10692)	Malvaceae		2015
<i>Sida</i> sp. L (A.M. Ashby 4202)	Malvaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Sida</i> sp. Pilbara (A.A.Mitchell PRP1543)	Malvaceae		2025 2021
<i>Sida</i> sp. spiciform panicles (E. Leyland s.n. 14/8/1990)	Malvaceae		2016 2015
<i>Sida spinosa</i>	Malvaceae	Spiny Sida	2025 2021 2015
<i>Sida trichopoda</i>	Malvaceae		2016 2015
* <i>Sigesbeckia orientalis</i>	Asteraceae	Indian Weed	2015
^{P3} <i>Solanum albostellatum</i>	Solanaceae		2016
<i>Solanum centrale</i>	Solanaceae	Desert Raisin	2016
<i>Solanum cleistogamum</i>	Solanaceae		2016
<i>Solanum diversiflorum</i>	Solanaceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Solanum elatius</i>	Solanaceae		2015
<i>Solanum ferocissimum</i>	Solanaceae		2015
<i>Solanum lasiophyllum</i>	Solanaceae	Flannel Bush	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Solanum morrisonii</i>	Solanaceae		2016
<i>Solanum perarmatum</i>	Solanaceae		2025
<i>Solanum phlomoides</i>	Solanaceae		2025 2015
* <i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	Asteraceae	Common Sowthistle	2016 2015
<i>Spermacoce brachystema</i>	Rubiaceae		2025 2015
<i>Sporobolus actinocladus</i>	Poaceae	Ray Grass	2025
<i>Sporobolus australasicus</i>	Poaceae	Fairy Grass	2025 2021 2016 2015

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Stackhousia</i> sp. Swollen gynophore (W.R. Barker 2041) W.R.Barker	Celastraceae		2015
<i>Stemodia grossa</i>	Plantaginaceae	Marsh Stemodia	2025 2015
<i>Stemodia kingii</i>	Plantaginaceae		2016 2015
<i>Stenopetalum anfractum</i>	Brassicaceae		2016
<i>Stenopetalum nutans</i>	Brassicaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Streptoglossa adscendens</i>	Asteraceae		2016
<i>Streptoglossa bubakii</i>	Asteraceae		2025 2016 2015
<i>Streptoglossa cylindriceps</i>	Asteraceae		2016 2015
<i>Streptoglossa decurrens</i>	Asteraceae		2025
<i>Streptoglossa liatroides</i>	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Streptoglossa macrocephala</i>	Asteraceae		2016
<i>Streptoglossa odora</i>	Asteraceae		2025 2016
^{P3} <i>Streptoglossa</i> sp. Cracking clays (S. van Leeuwen et al. PBS 7353)	Asteraceae		2025
<i>Striga squamigera</i>	Orobanchaceae		2015
<i>Stylobasium spathulatum</i>	Surianaceae	Pebble Bush	2021 2016 2015
<i>Swainsona decurrens</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Swainsona formosa</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Swainsona kingii</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Swainsona leeana</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Swainsona stenodonta</i>	Fabaceae		2025
^{P3} <i>Swainsona thompsoniana</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Synaptantha tillaeacea</i> var. <i>tillaeacea</i>	Rubiaceae		2025 2015
<i>Tephrosia densa</i>	Fabaceae		2025
<i>Tephrosia rosea</i> var. <i>clementii</i>	Fabaceae		2015
<i>Tephrosia rosea</i> var. Fortescue creeks (M.I.H. Brooker 2186)	Fabaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Tephrosia</i> sp. Bungaroo Creek (M.E. Trudgen 11601)	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Tephrosia</i> sp. Clay soils (S. van Leeuwen et al. PBS 0273)	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Tephrosia</i> sp. NW Eremaean (S. van Leeuwen et al. PBS 0356)	Fabaceae		2025 2015
<i>Tephrosia supina</i>	Fabaceae		2025
^{P2} <i>Teucrium pilbaranum</i>	Lamiaceae		2015
^{P3} <i>Themeda</i> sp. Hamersley Station (M.E. Trudgen 11431)	Poaceae		2025
<i>Themeda triandra</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Trachymene oleracea</i> subsp. <i>oleracea</i>	Araliaceae		2015
<i>Tragus australianus</i>	Poaceae	Small Burrgrass	2021 2015
<i>Trianthema glossostigmum</i>	Aizoaceae		2025 2015
<i>Trianthema triquetrum</i>	Aizoaceae	Red Spinach	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Trianthema turgidifolium</i>	Aizoaceae		2016
<i>Tribulopsis angustifolia</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2015
^{P3} <i>Tribulus adelacanthus</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2016
<i>Tribulus astrocarpus</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Tribulus hirsutus</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Tribulus macrocarpus</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2021
<i>Tribulus platypterus</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Cork Hopbush	2025 2015
<i>Tribulus suberosus</i>	Zygophyllaceae		2025
<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i> var. <i>zeylanicum</i>	Boraginaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Trigastrotheca molluginea</i>	Molluginaceae		2025 2021 2015
<i>Triodia angusta</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016
<i>Triodia basedowii</i>	Poaceae	Lobed Spinifex	2016

Taxon Name	Family	Common Name	Year Recorded
<i>Triodia brizoides</i>	Poaceae		2025 2015
<i>Triodia epactia</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Triodia glabra</i>	Poaceae		2025
<i>Triodia lanigera</i>	Poaceae		2025
<i>Triodia longiceps</i>	Poaceae	Giant Grey Spinifex	2025 2016 2015
<i>Triodia melvillei</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Triodia pungens</i>	Poaceae	Soft Spinifex	2016 2015
<i>Triodia schinzii</i>	Poaceae	Feathertop Spinifex	2016
<i>Triodia scintillans</i>	Poaceae		2015
<i>Triodia vanleeuwenii</i>	Poaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Triodia wiseana</i>	Poaceae	Limestone Spinifex	2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Tripogonella loliiformis</i>	Poaceae	Five Minute Grass	2025 2016 2015
<i>Triraphis mollis</i>	Poaceae	Needle Grass	2021
<i>Triumfetta chaetocarpa</i>	Malvaceae	Urchins	2025
<i>Triumfetta clementii</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Triumfetta johnstonii</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Triumfetta maconochieana</i>	Malvaceae		2021
<i>Typha domingensis</i>	Typhaceae	Bulrush	2015
<i>Urochloa occidentalis</i> var. <i>ciliata</i>	Poaceae		2025 2021
<i>Urochloa occidentalis</i> var. <i>occidentalis</i>	Poaceae		2025 2016
* <i>Vachellia farnesiana</i>	Fabaceae		2025 2021 2016 2015
<i>Vigna</i> sp. McDonald Downs Station (R.A. Perry 3416)	Fabaceae		2021 2016 2015
<i>Vincetoxicum lineare</i>	Apocynaceae	Bush Bean	2021 2016
<i>Vittadinia eremaea</i>	Asteraceae		2025
^{P3} <i>Vittadinia</i> sp. Coondewanna Flats (S. van Leeuwen 4684)	Asteraceae		2015
<i>Wahlenbergia tumidifructa</i>	Campanulaceae		2021 2015
<i>Waltheria virgata</i>	Malvaceae		2025
<i>Xerochloa barbata</i>	Poaceae	Rice Grass	2015

We at TERN acknowledge the traditional owners and their custodianship of the lands on which TERN operates. We pay our respects to their ancestors and their descendants, who continue cultural and spiritual connections to country.

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